

The Myths of “Virtual Harmlessness” and “Innocent Fantasy”: Sexual-Violence Scripts and Real-World Risks in ACG and Adult Anime

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Abstract

Taking the common defenses of “virtual harmlessness” and “innocent fantasy” as its organizing thread, this article develops a two-part argument. The first part synthesizes empirical research on sexually violent pornography, female-objectifying media, and the limited existing work on Hentai, and points out that exposure to content featuring sexual violence and objectification is associated with heightened aggression, reduced empathy toward victims, and increased rape myth acceptance and proclivity toward sexual aggression. Drawing on observations of on-site sexual harassment at anime conventions, bodily gazes directed at cosplayers, and joking or derisive commentary, it further shows how virtual scripts are re-enacted and normalized in offline interactions, thereby undermining the myth of “virtual harmlessness.” Building on this, the second part proposes the “Swiss-cheese × Pyramid” model of sexual-violence risk, which stratifies behavioral levels from L0 (attitudes and fantasies) to L3 (non-consensual penetrative assault), and distinguishes a high-risk population of potential perpetrators jointly produced by structural conditions and exposure to extreme pornography. The article argues that violent scripts which appear to “remain only in fantasy” can, by expanding the L0 base, increase the overall scale of sexual violence. At the same time, it notes that systematic empirical research on Hentai remains scarce, and that the inferences advanced here require further testing in future studies.

Keywords

ACG culture; adult anime; Hentai; virtual harmlessness; innocent fantasy; sexual scripts; sexual violence; sexual harassment at anime conventions; “Swiss-cheese × Pyramid” model of sexual-violence risk; potential perpetrators (L0)

Preface

In the preceding text (Zhu, J. 2025), we conducted an analysis of ACG culture and its derivative animated pornography (Hentai) from a theoretical standpoint, drawing upon classical Marxism and contemporary feminist theories, and unveiled the underlying logic of

consumption. However, despite extensive theoretical discussion, without empirical data to underpin these viewpoints, they remain tenuous and unsubstantial constructs. In the subsequent sections, I will integrate the academic research I have examined, endeavoring to correlate these scholarly findings with my theoretical arguments, thereby constructing a preliminary individual logic chain of viewership.

Regarding adult pornography, since its emergence in the last century until the present day, it has remained a subject of ongoing controversy. In this domain, academic resources are relatively abundant. In contrast, research on adult animation (Hentai) is markedly scarce. Based on my observations, it is more frequently incorporated within the broader category of general pornography, rather than being considered and addressed as a distinct subject. However, as previously articulated from a theoretical standpoint, this pornographic medium wields global influence, alongside an escalating severity in the depiction of sexual crimes within virtual contexts.

In response to this situation, Tokyo stands as a typical example of proactive interventions implemented over the past two decades. In 2010, the Tokyo Metropolitan Government enacted the Tokyo Metropolitan Ordinance on Healthy Development of Youth, the primary purpose of which was to broaden the definition of "harmful content" to include any anime, manga, or non-realistic imagery depicting illegal sexual acts or pseudo-sexual acts as defined in real life (such as rape, sexual assault), or those depicting illegal sexual acts or pseudo-sexual acts between close relatives, which have been improperly glorified or exaggerated. When sold in physical venues (such as bookstores or comic shops), these materials must, in principle, be labeled as "harmful publications," displayed in segregated sections, and purchasers are subject to age verification[80].

Pornographic depictions of minors frequently appear alongside the portrayal of illegal or pseudo-illegal sexual acts. Michiko Nagaoko, director of the Kyoto-based non-profit organization Juvenile Guide (NPO), reported that approximately 2,000 adult animations are released annually in Japan, half of which predominantly feature schoolgirl characters [81]. Before the revision of the Tokyo Metropolitan Youth Healthy Development Ordinance, the Tokyo Metropolitan Government attempted to introduce a regulation aimed at restricting the sexual depiction of 'non-existent youths' (非实在青少年), that is, fictional characters who appear under the age of 18; however, this faced strong opposition from manga artists and legal organizations within the industry and was ultimately withdrawn [82]. At times, 'freedom' and 'equality' stand in direct opposition.

Based on existing empirical research, I will refute the typical argument of such opponents: virtual content does not affect reality; it is merely a manifestation of individual fantasy, which, although potentially extreme, is harmless (here termed the "Virtual Is Harmless" thesis), and

demonstrate the difficulty of sustaining this view in empirical studies.

In conclusion, let the fire rise.

Virtual Harmlessness? How Viewing Shapes Cognition

In this paper, we have also repeatedly articulated the logic of domination represented behind viewing softcore content in ACG culture and Hentai works. These perspectives remain lacking in empirical validation; however, it is possible to delineate a logical progression from 'viewing to enactment' based on existing research outcomes. Before proceeding, several contentious issues must be resolved.

The primary argument advanced by proponents of virtual extreme sexual content and virtual child imagery pornography holds that virtuality and reality should not be conflated: 'Otaku are simply interested in two-dimensional characters,' and 'lolicon is not equivalent to pedophilia.' Lolicon (ロリコン) denotes individuals attracted to virtual depictions of young or childlike females, toward whom they develop romantic or even sexual desires. If the word 'virtual' were removed, one might say: 'Isn't this pedophilia!' This perspective is not surprising, as the issue itself remains highly contentious. For example, legal scholar Nakasatomi Hiroshi argues that in such virtual works, 'children endure relentless sexual abuse, torture, and exploitation in a considerably explicit manner,' advocating for the inclusion of virtual child pornography within the legal definition of child pornography (Nakasatomi Hiroshi, 2012). Opponents, such as anthropologist Patrick W. Galbraith, maintain that (creators of lolicon-style works) are merely manipulating symbols and engaging with characters—this neither reflects sexual pathology nor incites criminal behavior [84].

Based on existing research findings, two points can be established. First, **viewing animated pornography, as opposed to live-action pornography, more significantly predicts the use of sexual assault strategies in specific populations, with this relationship mediated by rape myth acceptance (RMA);** Second,¹ viewing animated pornography does not diminish 'sexual

¹ The concept of rape myths encompasses erroneous or biased public perceptions concerning rape acts or the typical behavioral responses of victims, such as endorsing the notions that 'women who wear short skirts or tight clothing are inviting rape,' 'women who are raped often bear some responsibility, especially if they voluntarily enter a male's residence or vehicle,' and that 'rape only constitutes sexual acts involving physical force accompanied by visible injuries.' Acceptance of these erroneous beliefs is highly likely to reduce public empathy toward victims, increase the likelihood of exonerating perpetrators, and potentially affect judicial decisions. Consequently, this causes victims to internalize such erroneous cognition or to fear societal condemnation, making them more inclined to forgo reporting the perpetrator, thereby emboldening perpetrators to commit sexual assaults against women with greater impunity.

attraction' toward real women.

1.1 Viewing frequency of animated pornography more significantly predicts the use of sexual assault strategies in specific populations

A recent study by the University of Porto, Portugal, sampled 906 university students (533 males and 373 females) and measured viewing frequency/duration of animated pornography among self-reported current users of adult animation, alongside rape myth acceptance and sexual assault strategies (SABS), using an online questionnaire. Research findings indicate that among male and female subjects, the viewing frequency of animated pornography is significantly associated with the propensity for sexual assault behaviors, with acceptance of rape myths playing a critical mediating role between viewing frequency and sexual assault strategies. The model accounts for approximately 25% to 37% of the variance in sexual assault strategies.

Let us analyze these data group by group, starting with rape myths. In this sample, the frequency of animated pornography consumption is significantly positively correlated with rape myth acceptance (RMA), which illustrates a particular issue: rape myth acceptance measurements reflect individuals' cognition of rape acts, comparable to endorsing myths such as 'she was raped because she dressed provocatively' or 'she went alone to a man's house late at night intending to be assaulted.' Moreover, without controlling for any variables, the direct effect between viewing frequency and sexual assault strategies remains significant; After incorporating rape myth acceptance (RMA) into the model, the direct effect diminished from significant to non-significant, thereby indicating complete mediation. This signifies that in the present study, animated pornography does not simply increase sexual assault strategies through sexual arousal, but rather operates by endorsing beliefs such as 'the victim is to blame,' 'women seduce me,' and 'women say no but actually mean yes,' thereby lowering individuals' risk sensitivity and vigilance toward such behaviors and enhancing the propensity to endorse sexual assault strategies through cognition serving as the mediating mechanism. The causal chain supported by this research is thus:

Viewing frequency ↑ → observable increase in acceptance of rape myths ↑ → which may thereby influence sexual assault strategies ↑

When controlling for acceptance of rape myths, the direct path from viewing frequency to

Simultaneously, the acceptance of these 'rape myths' may also influence males themselves, as endorsing such myths increases the likelihood of them committing assaults against women under normal or specific conditions (e.g., intoxication, drug use).

sexual assault strategies is no longer significant (complete mediation).

The conclusion of this study indicates that the frequency of animated pornography use is positively correlated with acceptance of rape myths; specifically, within this sample, the greater the frequency of viewing animated pornography, the higher the individual's acceptance of rape myths scores. However, this study cannot determine whether a causal relationship exists between the viewing frequency of animated pornography and acceptance of rape myths; this question necessitates further investigation.

However, according to the theoretical framework presented herein, when an individual assumes the dominant position within a dominant-submissive relationship as virtually reenacted in reality, this virtual continuation of patriarchal logic may subsequently exert a reciprocal influence on reality. This occurs because the viewing of animated pornography, under certain circumstances, serves as a quasi-substitute for real interpersonal relationships, naturalizing and normalizing this intentionally guided position, thereby incorporating it into the rehearsal of sexual scripts. This rehearsal involves psychological scripts at the internal cognitive level, which, through ongoing fantasy rehearsals, compete with interpersonal scripts and may be partially internalized as the enactment of interpersonal scripts, ultimately prevailing in this contest. This theoretical framework partially explains how viewing may lead to an increased acceptance of rape myths; viewing operates as a process of 'learning,' and the subsequent rise in acceptance of rape myths represents the cognitive outcome of this internalization applied to interpersonal scripts.

Many mainstream views argue that 'viewing pornography does not immediately transform one into a rapist.' Within this logic, such a stance seems reasonable because even if acceptance of rape myths rises, the psychological script component still competes with the interpersonal script, requiring self-authorization before any enactment. Activating these two 'gates' concurrently necessitates the operation of moral disengagement mechanisms and specific temporal conditions. It is more accurate to say that portraying the pathway from 'viewing to acting' as a direct line is a reprehensible sleight of hand; even a six-year-old child would not begin swearing fluently immediately after watching cartoons, let alone an adult. The transition from 'learning to acting' is originally a rugged route fraught with multiple checkpoints, and the role of viewing animated pornography is to, alongside other mechanisms, forcefully breach these barriers, thereby facilitating the unimpeded progression of desire to its terminus.

The statements made by these individuals appear reasonable but evade more fundamental cognitive issues. Although the direct commission of crimes certainly merits greater caution, even if one does not directly commit criminal acts, can a dismissive remark blaming victims seeking help online or ignoring intoxicated women subjected to predatory behavior on the street truly cause no harm?

Next, the explanation of the variance in this data will be addressed. In brief, the central issue revealed by this data consistently revolves around one proposition — 'Can the effects of viewing animated pornography and live-action pornography be considered equivalently?'

First, an analysis focused on this issue will be undertaken. Intuitively, given the differences between real human representations and anime depictions in terms of referential reality and media attributes, the cognitive impact of viewing them should be distinctly considered. As critic Saitō Tamaki observed in *The Psychoanalysis of Fighting Beauties* (戦闘美少女の精神分析), otaku sexual desire 'is directed towards fictional girls,' constituting a form of desire aimed at highly symbolized characters; this desire pathway is relatively disconnected from real women and therefore does not necessarily imply hostility toward real women (Saitō, 2011/2000).

However, even if 'desire' can temporarily retreat into what is termed 'virtual,' we must still recognize that the viewing scripts it employs fundamentally reproduce real-world dominant-submissive relationships. It instructs the individual not only on 'whom one should desire' but also on 'how one may desire.' Although the object may be virtual, the script of domination remains transferable. As Simon and Gagnon have argued, once an individual discovers a behavioral script that reliably elicits sexual pleasure, it becomes psychologically fixed or quasi-ritualized. When an individual perceives the dominant script applied to a virtual female image as a 'formula' that consistently produces pleasure, this logic gradually consolidates and becomes difficult to undermine under specific conditions.

It is more accurate to assert that the logic of domination present in reality is perpetuated within the 'harmless' virtual space and is continuously amplified within this fantasy realm. Desire may be dissociated, but the script cannot be escaped. It is progressively internalized within the subject according to the logic of sexual scripts. Otherwise, in the aforementioned empirical research, the acceptance of rape myths should not increase in tandem with viewing frequency—but the data reveal the exact opposite. The higher the viewing frequency, the greater the endorsement of rape myths. Does this not sufficiently demonstrate that this domination script, deemed virtual and harmless, has, in fact, been absorbed and internalized by viewers, thereby actively contributing to the reproduction of reality?

During the research process, observable differences in sexual assault strategies among participants were identified. It is established that the viewing frequency of animated pornography can predict the acceptance of rape myths and sexual assault strategies; within their model, this effect is quantified by measuring all three variables. The variance explained (R^2) indicates the extent to which differences in the sexual assault strategy scale among individuals can be accounted for by the viewing frequency of animated pornography.

In brief, individual differences in sexual assault strategies are influenced by multiple factors such as personal experiences and cultural contexts, yet the viewing frequency of animated

pornography alone accounts for one-quarter to one-third of this variance, comparable to the potentially long-standing societal misconceptions accumulated over several years. Furthermore, in the same study, the correlation between the viewing frequency of general live-action pornography and rape myths or sexual assault strategies is considerably weaker; in certain gender groups, mediation models could not even be established. In other words, within this sample, the viewing frequency of animated pornography significantly better explains individual differences in sexual assault strategies than live-action pornography.

The sole limitation is that this thesis employed a cross-sectional design among individuals, thus precluding further verification of differences in sexual assault strategies before and after longitudinal exposure to animated versus live-action pornography. Nonetheless, based on this rare study of Hentai works viewing, several inferences and explanations can be advanced.

Firstly, this pertains to the attitudes toward viewing live-action pornography versus animated pornography. Why does the frequency of viewing animated pornography, despite both types being pornographic content, much better explain differences in sexual assault strategies than the frequency of viewing live-action pornography? The extent to which this is related to the inherent stylistic depiction in animated pornography remains unknown; however, the results indicate that the strong explanatory power of animated pornography frequency for individual differences in sexual assault strategies precisely demonstrates the close association between this type of animated pornographic content and sexual assault strategies. I contend that this association is manifested in the widespread presence of extreme themes within animated pornography.

To elucidate this point, we may turn our attention to the contrasting category of live-action pornography. Compared to animated pornography, depictions of sexual assault in live-action pornography have received considerably more early scrutiny, as such productions inherently inflict varying degrees of harm on female performers. This constitutes a direct violation of human rights, and feminist criticism of it has been continuous. Just prior to the publication of this article in 2021, through the concerted efforts of various industry stakeholders, the world's largest pornography website, Pornhub, was compelled to conduct a comprehensive purge of videos containing 'minor participation' and 'depictions of sexual offenders,' reportedly removing as many as 8.8 million videos in total [85]. Subsequently, an observable phenomenon is that when one attempts to enter keywords such as 'rape' in the site's search bar, the platform returns no video results and issues a warning. Similarly, when searching for keywords such as 'rape video' on the Google search engine, the returned search results do not include direct pornography videos.

This, to some extent, reflects that live-action pornography depicting sexual crime is gradually shifting from being rampant to being subject to control and removal. In certain countries, possession of works containing depictions of sexual offenders is considered illegal and has even

been explicitly incorporated into the law (e.g., in the United Kingdom). These measures have significantly hindered the circulation of live-action pornography with sexual offender themes.

Within the extensive body of research on live-action pornography, most studies focus on videos or slideshows depicting sexual violence and sexual assault, with findings primarily based on the consumption of extreme pornography. Therefore, in this study conducted after the regulation of extreme pornography products commenced, the explanatory power of live-action pornography, limited to only 1%, is also justifiable. Furthermore, this may inversely suggest that precisely because of the widespread presence of sexual assault themes in Hentai works—which have not been afforded comparable scrutiny as live-action pornography and have been broadly circulated under the rationale of 'this is only drawn' or 'this is only fantasy'—the frequency of consuming animated pornography accounts for approximately one-third to one-quarter of the variance in sexual assault strategies. This is more accurately described not as 'animated pornography being inherently more harmful,' but rather as 'extreme sexual domination scripts being presented more fully and without consequences in animation,' thereby magnifying its statistical correlation with sexual assault strategies.

1.2 Animated pornography enthusiasts have not exhibited a diminished

“sexual attraction” toward real women.

A study published in the academic journal *Sexologies* found that hentai consumers rated their attraction to animated characters significantly higher than other participants, while showing no difference in attraction to real human images. Their romantic desire toward animated characters exceeded that of other participants, yet no difference was observed in romantic desire toward real individuals.

The article titled *The differentiation between consumers of hentai pornography and live-action pornography* utilized a sample of 208 university students, comprising 75 males and 133 females. Among them, 28.8% self-identified as consumers of animated pornography within the past year, 38.0% as non-consumers of animated pornography, and 33.2% as non-consumers of pornography. Accordingly, researchers categorized the subjects into three groups: the Hentai viewing group, the live-action pornography viewing group, and the non-pornography viewing group. Notably, the vast majority of animated pornography enthusiasts in this experiment also consumed live-action pornographic content, with only seven individuals exclusively consuming animated pornography.

During the experiment, subjects were first required to assess their adult attachment tendencies using an intimate relationship experience scale. Subsequently, subjects evaluated nine images of animated characters and nine images of live-action characters to measure the appeal of specific images to the participant group. In the subsequent scales measuring the desire for

romantic relationships and the consumption of pornographic content, participants were required to complete 10 to 15 items respectively, designed to assess their desire to establish romantic relationships with animated characters or real persons and to evaluate four motivations for consuming pornographic content (emotional escape, sexual curiosity, thrill seeking, and sexual pleasure).

The experimental results indicated no significant differences among the three groups with respect to 'avoidant attachment'. Differences in 'anxious attachment' were observed only among the female sample. The Hentai group rated the attractiveness of animated characters higher; however, their ratings of real persons' attractiveness did not differ from those of other groups. The Hentai group exhibits a significantly stronger desire to 'establish romantic relationships with animated characters'; however, there is no intergroup difference in the desire to 'engage in romantic relationships with live-action individuals.' Regarding consumption motives, it is noteworthy that male subjects demonstrate higher motivation to consume Hentai in the 'seeking excitement' dimension compared to live-action pornography.

The significance of this article's findings lies not only in its rare empirical investigation of differences between animated pornography consumers and live-action pornography consumers but also in its robust refutation, from a scientific research perspective, of the cognition that 'anime enthusiasts are solely interested in animated characters.' Empirically, it provides new evidence supporting the practice of individuals translating virtual viewing experiences back into reality.

As the research findings demonstrate, although animated pornography enthusiasts may indeed exhibit a greater attraction to animated characters and a desire to form romantic relationships with them, their attraction to live-action characters and desire to establish romantic relationships may not significantly differ from those of the general population. This, therefore, redirects the issue to the viewing scripts of animated pornography. If their desire for live-action individuals remains undiminished, then conversely. We have repeatedly raised and argued whether the dominant-submissive relationships and sexual scripts internalized from animated pornography may be reactivated in reality.

Within the original context, categorizing Hentai works depicting sexual crimes as 'harmful' in Japan reveals that official discourse includes perspectives suggesting that the attitude towards such works is 'perceived as harmful,' albeit 'primarily based on intuition.' The stance towards animated pornography enthusiasts who favor these works can be interpreted as 'cognitively harmful but behaviorally inconclusive regarding harm.' However, is this truly the case? When dominant-submissive relationships are replicated and continuously internalized in the virtual domain, and scripts of sexual offenders are repeatedly rehearsed within this so-called 'harmless space,' it cannot simply be labeled as 'harmless' or 'mere fantasy,' because fantasies can sometimes cause harm.

Sexual Harassment at Comic Conventions: What Is the Core Issue?

The most direct evidence of this is the sexual harassment of live-action cosplayers at comic conventions. When many people think of comic conventions, they may envision grand exhibition halls, cosplayers dressed valiantly, and enthusiastic fans. Yet, alongside these thriving scenes, there exists pervasive sexual harassment and sexual degradation of cosplayers.

Sexual harassment of cosplayers by visitors at two-dimensional comic conventions (such as anime and manga fan events) has been extensively reported and verified. Extensive evidence indicates that this is not an isolated case but a systemic problem occurring across comic conventions globally. In Europe and North America, this form of sexual harassment has even been given a specific name: 'Con Creeping' (漫展猥褻).

How widespread is this phenomenon? For example, a comprehensive survey conducted in 2014 by comics critic Janelle Asselin on sexual harassment within the comic convention domain found that 59% of respondents acknowledged the presence of harassment in the community, and 25% self-reported experiencing some form of sexual harassment [86]. In a 2014 field survey conducted at the Colombia Comic Convention, one of the largest comic conventions worldwide, nearly one-quarter of female cosplayers reported to the organizers that they had experienced non-consensual physical harassment, including being touched by strangers without permission and having their skirts lifted suddenly for covert photography [87].

Moreover, numerous interviews with cosplayers indicate that these forms of sexual harassment are varied and difficult to prevent. For example, a cosplay enthusiast who attended the Colombia Comic Convention reported experiencing sexual harassment multiple times during her participation in conventions; the worst incident involved a male who, under the pretense of taking photographs, embraced her and attempted to touch her buttocks. One interviewee, who was only 17 years old at the time, was subjected to a prolonged and uncomfortable embrace by a male attendee during the event. Furthermore, in interviews with other media outlets, they were asked offensive questions such as "breast size" and "whether they chose the most sexually provocative attire" [88]. I contend that such phenomena are by no means isolated incidents, but rather structural problems that inevitably emerge when sexuality is fetishized as an inherent female essence. Sexual harassment represents the ultimate manifestation of this issue.

Jim C. Hines, a science fiction writer and a staff member at a rape crisis center, has noted that, beyond sexual harassment, victim-blaming is also widespread at comic conventions [89]. Many people take it for granted that wearing revealing clothing justifies arbitrary behavior towards Cosers. Many argue that 'this type of sexy attire is intended to attract attention and

seduce men'; this cognition, however, is better understood as resulting from the association between sexualization and male orientation. Individuals, habituated to characters responding to desire in games and anime series, internalize sexual scripts of female submission

and pleasure through repeated enactment and reinforcement within the two-dimensional environment.

This signboard was photographed at a comic convention. It depicts several males covertly photographing an unsuspecting female Coser using various photographic equipment. Furthermore, this may represent only the tip of the iceberg of what nearly one-quarter of female victims have endured [90].

Evidently, in real-life settings most closely aligned with ACG culture—comic conventions—the cognition of the logic of domination and sexual scripts is most prominently expressed. Recalling Ueno Chizuko's observation, society restricts women to a dichotomous identity of either 'saint' or 'prostitute.' When female cosplayers at comic conventions are perceived as violating feminine norms, and their revealing attire is regarded as a sign of impurity, such observers cognitively define them solely as 'prostitutes,' who exist to serve male sexuality. They also extend this cognition to Cosers without concern.

This form of cognition culturally confines women to exist as entities to be possessed. At comic conventions, this cultural script is legitimately reenacted under the auspices of 'photography' and 'interaction.' This cognition also stems from the strong association between sexuality and female identity; when sexuality is conceptualized as an integrated notion imbued with 'moe attribute' connotations, female cosplayers embodying these 'moe attributes' likewise perpetuate this cognitive framework, being perceived as objects of sexuality. Consequently, from a structural standpoint, Cosers materialize the anime female image as a vessel of desire in the real world.

When viewers leave inappropriate remarks in the comment section about a cosplayer faithfully portraying a character, such as “she is so slutty ” or “she sexually arouses me,” they not only reduce the woman’s value to her level of sexuality but also replicate the phenomenon of virtual attribute fetishism. What the audience conveys is not that the individual herself provokes their sexual arousal, but that their sexual desire is triggered by her as an assemblage of attributes. Directing this attribute-induced sexual desire toward the specific individual constitutes a reenactment of fetishism—the attribute of sexual desirability appears forcibly bound to her essence.

At comic conventions, when a cosplayer who should be separated from the character they portray (since the cosplayer merely replicates the character) is instead regarded as an agent of that character, attribute fetishism directed at the character extends to the cosplayer. The root cause of sexual harassment thereby becomes apparent — not only arising from societal constructions of women, nor solely from the misogyny articulated by Ueno Chizuko, but also embedded within the logic of domination promoted as 'harmless' in virtual contexts.

This precisely demonstrates that, whether concerning animated characters or cosplayers, their value within player communities is determined by the attributes assigned to them. This mode of value assessment is simply an extension of players projecting their desires onto attributes. Players are concerned not with the character itself, but with the attributes it embodies. Thus, when these attributes of animated characters are manifested in live-action characters, the cognition of the dominant-submissive relationship remains operative, as the constellation of attributes is transferred to the cosplayer, who thereby becomes a tangible proxy for desire. Whether it involves fantasies of violating animated characters or the actual sexual harassment of live-action characters, the underlying target is the same: to evoke a response to the attributes. However, the sexual harassment observed at comic conventions manifests a sequential logic of 'rehearsed in the virtual, enacted in the real.'When the projection of such desires attains unrestricted satisfaction within the virtual realm, and the script of domination becomes entrenched in reality, cosplayers, as the nexus between virtuality and reality, inevitably bear the primary burden of this scripted domination.

Nevertheless, although sexual harassment and covert filming are pervasive, at present, are these not predominantly issues at the individual level? Ultimately, can these problems be mitigated to minimal consequences through enhanced regulation and the establishment of sexual harassment response mechanisms? This question aside from the practical extent to which organizers are willing to implement such theoretical risk reductions. Under certain circumstances, not only do substantive illegal acts such as covert filming and sexual harassment occur, but the logic of domination and sexualization persists even in recordings that appear to be compliant.

Image source: Firefly Comic Convention | Review of the first day at the Valkyrie Training Camp event [91]

Even the acts of viewing and filming can sometimes reproduce power imbalances. This photograph was taken at the Firefly Comic Convention in Guangzhou, where a female cosplayer on stage was placed inside a glass display case, striking various poses for attendees below to photograph. The Coser on stage appeared as a highly anticipated idol, prompting several audience members to involuntarily raise their phones to record. However, filming within this cage-like display case evokes a voyeuristic sensation akin to that of observing animals. It is more precise to state that, in this photograph, the female Cosers have been dehumanized into sexual commodities intended for visual consumption. Ironically, the most compelling evidence for this assessment comes from an official acknowledgment: the imitation of the “ten-pull” gacha system from the game 'Nikki: Goddess of Victory' [92] — suggesting that the female Cosers here symbolize commodities to be acquired and evaluated based on rarity, degree of exposure, and sensuality.

The actors are confined within display cases, existing as passive objects, while the audience, as viewing subjects, possess the power to select, capture, and disseminate the gaze. In this composition, the mobile phone's lens substitutes for the eye, and the tacit consensus among the crowd creates a low-angle, densely concentrated spectacle of filming. Through the spatial separation effected by glass, the 'domination–subordination' script is materialized into an

objectively unequal viewing logic. Women are exhibited as commodities confined within cages. The spectators below resemble ravenous wolves, greedily fixating on every exposed patch of skin revealed by the women inside the showcase. The cosplayers on stage, akin to salivating fresh meat, are compelled to endure a variety of malevolent gazes. Women become restricted spectacles subject to voyeuristic observation.

The audience's low-angle, upward viewing and photographing of second-tier cosplayers directs focus toward the thighs, hips, and skirt hems, thereby intensifying the dehumanization of female cosplayers. The stage arrangement—comprising glass cases and backlighting—unequivocally serves to better showcase the female body. Collectively, these elements transform the scene into a grand ceremonial shrine. The essential purpose of this ritual is to sanctify the object of 'offering' and to suspend its bodily agency. This ritualized mode of viewing simultaneously deepens the cognition of power relations, naturalizing the inequality inside and outside the display case as a 'game feature,' thereby positioning the player within a fixed logic of domination without moral reservation; through this cognition, the player repeatedly internalizes and reenacts this operation, thus reproducing domination.

Capital commodifies women in virtual spaces, attaching their value to rarity, degree of exposure, and sensuality, thereby reproducing the logic of domination present in reality. Those who bear the cost of this capitalistic sexual commodification are real-life cosplayers, who must wear attire as revealing and sexualized as that of animated characters, serving as the physical embodiments of these sensual personas, referred to by players as character reenactments. Simultaneously, they must also endure the malicious gazes originally directed at virtual characters. Multiple interviews with cosplayers illustrate this phenomenon.

For example, Molly McIssac is a cosplay enthusiast, but when she mustered the courage to wear a tight-fitting costume, she was repeatedly photographed without consent; she stated that this made her feel 'violated and alienated' [93]. Patricia Hernandez explicitly stated in her report that 'these cosplayers have had enough of being treated as 'meat objects''[94]. A cosplayer interviewed on the eve of Japan's 2019 Comiket confirmed that voyeuristic photography does indeed occur; when in a crowd, individuals openly sit cross-legged to take low-angle shots, causing them significant distress[95]. They emphasized that even if such photography is conducted publicly, it should not be taken for granted. The severity of this voyeuristic photography has even compelled cosplayers to consider restricting their shoots to one-on-one sessions with acquaintances to avoid harassment, thereby being forced to withdraw from public spaces, and through self-imposed limitations to ensure safety.

I contend that this is certainly not because their experiences are extreme isolated cases, but rather because only they have withstood the pressure to speak out. Beneath them lies the silent majority (Silent Majority), countless tears blended with helplessness, innumerable fears of human

rights violations, and innumerable cosplay enthusiasts who never dare to attend comic conventions again.

Moreover, we can further substantiate this perspective by examining issues of sexual harassment against cosplayers at comic conventions and the underlying viewing logic: if real-life cosplayers are subjected to such widespread sexual harassment and malicious gazes, then if animated characters possessed their own volition, one can only imagine how many grievances remain unvoiced in this coerced performance. As observed by the British Daily Mail, the malicious harassment directed at cosplayers who portray animated characters in revealing attire further demonstrates the widespread objectification of female images in anime [96].

On this basis, we analyze an extreme case, offering a concise examination from the perspective of the spectacularization of women, and explicate how this virtual viewing logic influences reality and becomes internalized as behavioral norms within individuals. The ultimate objective is to counter the claim that 'the virtual does not translate into reality.' Clearly, when the sexualized virtual domination script exerts an objective influence upon the scripts governing real interpersonal relationships, it no longer constitutes a harmless cultural feature. When 'sexiness' is naturalized as an inherent female essence and the camera is implicitly assumed to grant a right of disposition, comic conventions become experimental sites where virtual sexual scripts migrate into reality—even if no laws are violated, domination is still operative. This also represents a genuine reflection of the persistent desire for the virtual, as well as the extension of the logic of domination from the virtual realm into reality.

1.3 The Collapse of 'Virtual Harmlessness': Objectification, Sexual Violence Scripts, and Real-World Risks in ACG/Adult Animation

If we aspire to render the 'harmful' experiences within ACG culture and adult animation theoretically substantial, empirically observable, explicable, and demonstrable, the foremost prerequisite is to comprehensively dismantle the defense logic of 'virtual harmlessness.' In the preceding discussion, we refuted this logic and substantiated the theory of 'domination reproduction' from the dual perspectives of the works themselves and the viewers. Firstly, with respect to the works themselves, the observable phenomenon is that specific individuals (the sample population of this study, $n = 906$; males 533, females 373) exhibit a viewing frequency of adult animation that predicts their acceptance of rape myths (RMA) and sexual assault strategies (SABS); moreover, the viewing frequency of adult animation accounts for 25% to 37% of the variance in individuals' sexual assault strategies in the model (total explanatory power: male group $R^2 \approx .25$; female group $R^2 \approx .37$); All exhibit complete mediation; that is, under the measurements and samples used, the model-level explained variance can reach approximately one-third at most.

By combining the two, we can deduce that if an individual's sexual assault strategies are higher than those of others, their viewing frequency of animated pornography can account for one-third of the reason for this relative elevation; one explanation is that a high viewing frequency of animated pornography by the individual predicts elevated sexual assault strategies. However, the results of this study indicate correlation rather than direct causation (due to its cross-sectional design), meaning that an individual's frequency of viewing animated pornography may not be the sole cause of elevated sexual assault strategies; If an individual's sexual assault strategies are elevated, this may similarly lead to an increased frequency of viewing animated pornography.

Similarly, in another study, a subject group (n=208; male 75, female 133) completed self-report scales and image rating tasks. The experimental results indicated that although Hentai enthusiasts exhibited greater attraction and romantic desire toward animated characters, their attraction and romantic desire toward live-action characters did not differ from those of other control groups.

These phenomena suggest that specific Hentai enthusiasts do not diminish their attraction and romantic desire toward live-action characters despite an increased attraction and romantic desire toward animated characters. This conclusion is generally counterintuitive, as mainstream cognition often assumes that anime enthusiasts are socially withdrawn due to their reclusive traits, avoid reality, and therefore transfer their affectionate emotions to the virtual realm. Conversely, the experimental results remind us that the desire to establish real-world attachment relationships within such groups may never have disappeared, and this yearning is not attenuated by affection for Virtual relationships.

Similarly, historically, adult animation depicting sexual crime has been considered a 'harmful' yet 'freedom'-necessary phenomenon. Although the content is morally condemned, it is also understood to serve as a safety valve, functioning analogously to stress relief or an outlet for desire. The critical underpinning of this perspective is that mainstream society tends to view Hentai consumers as 'addicted to Virtuality and uninterested in reality.' Hence, even when the animated content is portrayed in extreme ways, it is regarded merely as a form of entertainment lifestyle, since even if consumers entertain various extreme thoughts about animated characters, these do not translate into real-world actions.

This experiment rigorously challenged and refuted the viewpoint with precise data, demonstrating that Hentai enthusiasts, despite potentially harboring desires to violate various animated characters, did not exhibit a diminished attraction toward real women. This is linked to sexual script theory, whereby the desires of Hentai consumers can be temporarily redirected toward animated characters, eliciting stronger emotional responses. However, the script gradually culminates in the rehearsal of fantasy behaviors through repeated enactments

involving spectacularization as domination, kawaii-ization of women, and moral disengagement regarding the self, thereby being cognitively recognized as an applicable and retrievable sexual script for the corresponding symbols. What Ueno describes as 'sexual arousal from symbols' fundamentally refers to this trajectory from symbol to script.

If it can be demonstrated that viewing adult animation influences reality, and that the consequences of such viewing may be more severe than those of live-action pornography. We may then attempt to reinterpret existing research findings on live-action viewing in relation to animation viewing, since the only difference lies in the object of viewing and domination, shifting from real women to animated characters. Naturally, this reflects a hesitant theoretical construction amidst the relative scarcity of research on Hentai and ACG culture; it functions more as a conjecture that can offer reference value but should not be construed as definitive research findings. Let us begin.

1.3.1 Objectification, Cinematography, and Body Gaze in ACG Culture

Firstly, the widespread phenomenon of objectification and body gaze occurs in male-oriented works within ACG culture. This phenomenon is primarily manifested in animated series, especially male-oriented anime series, where a salient feature is the abrupt appearance of close-up shots focusing on female body parts, exposing female characters' bodies to 'serve' the audience. In the Chinese context, this phenomenon is termed 'sha bi si,' originating from the English word 'service,' which was transcribed into Japanese katakana as サービス and subsequently transliterated. The depiction of this 'sha bi si' scenario typically occurs in various scenes that are not narratively essential (such as hot springs, seaside, changing rooms). For example, in a scene of a young girl bathing—a scene that could be omitted—the contours of breasts and semi-nude bodies are displayed; maid outfits, nurse uniforms, and bunny girl costumes appear without contextual justification (such as in officially released special editions). This form of 'service' scenario can also be audiovisual, including sexually suggestive panting sounds made by women during massages or tickling, or character ASMR outside the anime series[97].

Laura Mulvey, in **Visual Pleasure and Narrative Cinema**, argues that women in narrative films exist as encoded spectacles to be looked at (to-be-looked-at-ness), an indispensable element for display within mainstream narrative cinema. In such films, women function as 'the recipient of the male gaze' and 'an object of male desire.' However, this depiction of women as bodily displays within the space clearly causes transient interruptions to the narrative, thereby impacting its fluidity. Capital simultaneously integrates women as spectacles into the film narrative, while also having to concede that such integration disrupts narrative progression. Moreover, Mulvey further noted that mainstream narrative film developed a strategy of 'suturing-neutralization' to incorporate the spectator's extradiegetic desire into the narrative

through the male protagonist's gaze and actions, thereby skillfully resolving the tension between the dual functions of 'the woman to-be-looked-at' and 'the man who drives the narrative' (Laura Mulvey, 1975).

This stands in contrast to the narrative cinema criticized by Mulvey. The deliberately orchestrated 'sha bi si' scenes in animation are precisely intended for the display of the body. That is to say, whereas other films deliberately attempt to conceal explicit female imagery to avoid disrupting narrative progression, anime series instead openly embrace the presentation of such shots. In certain anime series, the exposure of the female body itself may function as part of the narrative for the audience, presented unreservedly before viewers, clearly manifesting a body gaze that caters to the audience. It does not necessarily increase explicitness but objectively achieves the objectification of women. This is precisely the aspect that warrants attention and critique.

Similarly, the audience's viewing desire can also be incorporated into the narrative through the actions and realization of the male protagonist. However, beneath the guise of virtual harmlessness, such narratives become more excessive. For example, in certain harem anime series and male-oriented anime series, there are 'unconscious' sexual harassment scenarios. Specifically, these narratives arrange for the male protagonist to suddenly fall or lunge at an attractive female character in hallways or open spaces, thereby depicting the female character's skirt being 'accidentally' torn to reveal underwear, or her shirt being torn to expose lingerie, and even instances of groping. This narrative device deliberately constructs the male protagonist's 'unconsciousness' (such protagonists are often referred to as 'fortunate perverts'), thereby absolving him of moral culpability for his sexual harassment (in some particular cases, the narrative even creates the false impression that women who resist sexual harassment are actually the perpetrators), in order to preserve the protagonist's positive characterization, while simultaneously indirectly displaying the female body to the audience through these actions. This constitutes a typical example of the spectacularization of display integrated into anime narratives.

It diminishes the seriousness of sexual harassment as a crime and trivializes it for entertainment purposes, thus becoming a form of 'service' for the audience. This depiction has been internalized as a manifestation of individual cognitive processes; for example, when 'unconscious' sexual harassment occurs, the untimely barrage comment of 'envying the male protagonist' reflects an almost fetishistic reverence for the female body and a minimization of the severity of sexual harassment.

A study on young women's attitudes toward the male gaze after exposure to magazine inserts with varying degrees of explicitness demonstrated that women exposed to more explicit inserts showed greater acceptance of the male gaze in both follow-up interviews and 48-hour

assessments compared to those exposed to less explicit inserts. This study further demonstrates that even brief exposure to explicit images in magazine inserts can have a lasting impact on societal attitudes toward women (Wright et al., 2014). In another empirical study published in the Archives of Sexual Behavior, researchers assessed the frequency of pornography consumption over the past year among 187 male university students attracted to women (n=187), the weekly duration of reading male-oriented magazines such as Maxim and Esquire, and the number of days per week watching reality shows like Jersey Shore and Real World. Data were then collected using scales measuring 'viewing women as sexual objects' and 'support for attitudes endorsing violence against women,' leading to critical findings. The research findings indicate that exposure to three types of media significantly increases the objectification of women (pornography $\beta = .24$, magazines $\beta = .20$, reality shows $\beta = .15$). The close similarity between the data on pornography exposure and male-oriented magazine exposure demonstrates that considerable objectification of women can occur even in the absence of direct explicit sexual content. This objectification of women also strongly predicts individuals' attitudes supporting violence against women, showing a complete mediation effect: this result suggests that even non-violent and non-explicit objectifying content can elevate tolerance of sexual violence through the schema of viewing women as sexual objects (Wright et al., 2016).

The significance of these two research findings lies in their transformation of the discomfort experienced through sensory objectification into rigorous empirical data. They also reaffirm the importance of resisting the objectification of women, as it is not merely a subjective perception but indeed exerts a cognitive impact and can be linked to the serious issue of attitudes toward violent aggression against women. This principle similarly applies to ACG culture; the aforementioned experiments successfully demonstrated the cognitive impact arising from objectification content involving real persons. Based on the conclusions of these experiments, we can reasonably infer that objectification and body gaze within ACG culture also have real-world effects. Under the mediation script of 'objectification of women,' this may similarly contribute to increased attitudes endorsing violent aggression against women, since the object of desire can be transferred to animated characters, but the desire scripts can be inversely shaped by the value systems conveyed through animations and, once firmly established, are difficult to alter. If subsequent research can directly demonstrate that this phenomenon is also reproduced within ACG culture, it would undoubtedly constitute a significant challenge to the pervasive yet disregarded objectification within ACG culture.

1.3.2 Violence, Aggressiveness, and Sexual Degradation in Hentai Works

Secondly, there is the widespread portrayal of violent violations, sexual crimes against women, and sexual degradation in adult animation. In the vast majority of works, female figures

or figures resembling women (such as cross-dressers) are objects of the gaze and form the principal focus of the visual representation. When presented as an object, it conveys the signal of being 'at the mercy of others' and 'lacking autonomous consciousness'; thus, such objectification is more prone to develop into unrestrained depictions of sexual assault.

Ueno Chizuko contends that the standard pattern embodied in mainstream pornography is a form of 'domination through pleasure,' whose core essence is the veneration of the belief that female pleasure derives from male sexual activity. This extends further to the reverence for the belief that female pleasure arises from male domination. A typical example is the depiction of pleasure on women's faces during sexual intercourse, a phenomenon so pervasive in various shunga paintings that it functions as an unwritten convention. Ueno asserts that what this fundamentally reveals is the pleasure derived from female subjugation.

The ongoing reproduction of depictions of sexual offenders and sexual degradation in adult animation rests precisely on the underlying structure that reveres 'pleasure derived from domination.' Women are attributed portrayals that are entirely inconsistent with reality, and even inverted; sexual harassment is portrayed as a form of eroticism, victims of sexual assault are misrepresented as inherently sexually frustrated, women become sexual instruments created solely for sexual purposes, and there is an attempt to frame this domination as women's own enjoyment of violence and violation. Women are depicted not only as tools serving male domination but also as actively obtaining pleasure through being dominated.

This is the most vivid manifestation of the assertion that 'the phallus is the center of pleasure'; male domination does not originate from the individual himself but rather from the social order that constructs the illusion of a 'Phallus.' In Lacanian psychoanalytic theory, this phallus serves as a signifier of power, whereas in adult animation it reverts to its most primordial referent—the 'penis' itself. Within this context, domination is manifested through the depiction of female desire for the 'penis.' Female sexual behavior does not revolve around any specific male individual; it may not even center on males at all (as in Futanari works, where even female characters endowed with a penis can occupy a dominant position). This is the critical point. Rather, it is the 'penis'; in sexual relations, a woman's active service to the 'penis' also symbolizes submission to absolute power. The penetration of the 'penis' into the woman signifies the conquest of the woman by absolute power. Within the context of adult animation, both behaviors undoubtedly reflect a belief in the domination of women.

Ueno interprets men's worship of domination as follows: in men's eyes, regardless of their social status, as long as they can achieve sexual domination over women, they can reverse all other negative factors; this is the root of such worship. Males are ascribed with the 'Phallus' and are socially informed that they possess power, integrity, and subjectivity; however, no male has ever truly possessed the 'Phallus.' He must continuously affirm his subjectivity by objectifying

the Other, where this Other refers to females. Consuming pornography is a ritual of subject confirmation, whose essence is to enable males to persistently reaffirm the 'Phallus' amid the growing fear of its loss, even if it remains illusory. Adult animation constitutes the most ideal venue for males to display this 'victory of the phallus.' It manifests domination in a more explicit and unrestrained manner, allowing males to attain a stronger sense of subjective identification.

The successful constitution of the domination subject depends on the spectacularization of sexual offenders, the female kawaii-ization, and the logic of moral disengagement directed at the viewer, ultimately completing the construction of sexual scripts. This returns us to our earlier discussion. Hypothetically, sexual scripts can be internalized through viewing and subsequently perpetuated in reality; this perspective is supported by numerous research findings and empirical data.

1.4 Psychological and behavioral consequences of viewing sexually violent content: aggressiveness, empathy, and rape myths

1.4.1 Short-term effects of viewing sexual violence

In 1981, the University of Wisconsin conducted an experimental study on the aggressiveness of individuals after viewing real sexual violence content (Donnerstein & Berkowitz, 1981). In Experiment 1, the researchers selected 80 male undergraduate participants (n=80) and assessed the degree of their aggressive behavior by varying the intensity of electric shocks delivered to a research assistant using a 'Bass' shock apparatus after viewing different types of videos. The specific procedure involved two researchers (one male and one female) first escorting each participant to a separate room to write an essay; subsequently, they deliberately provided negative feedback on the essay and administered a certain level of electric shock punishment to justifiably 'anger' the participant, who was then brought to the viewing room while still in an agitated state.

Eighty participants were instructed to watch four types of video clips: a talk show segment without pornographic content, a couple's sexual intercourse video without sexual violence content, or two pornographic films depicting sexual violence. These two sexual violence pornographic films used identical footage, differing only in the first and last 30 seconds, which portrayed the female victim's reactions differently: in the "positive portrayal" version, the female victim, after enduring rough abuse such as beating, binding, and slapping, did not resist but instead smiled, displaying pleasure; in the "negative manifestation" version, the victim showed resistance and emotions of pain, disgust, and fear.

After participants viewed one of the films, they were required to engage in a question-and-answer session with the research assistant who had previously 'provoked' them. For each incorrect answer given by the assistant, participants were free to select the intensity of an

electric shock, which was used to measure their aggressiveness toward the assistant following exposure to different films. Thereafter, participants were also required to complete a questionnaire assessing their emotional responses to the film content. The results of Experiment 1 demonstrated that participants administered significantly higher average electric shock intensities to the female assistant than to the male assistant after viewing sexually violent content, irrespective of whether the victim's response was active or passive; No significant increase was observed toward male targets (Donnerstein & Berkowitz, 1981). That is to say, the heightened aggressiveness following exposure to sexually violent content is not indiscriminate 'discharge,' but demonstrates clear gender specificity.

This phenomenon is explained in the text as a manifestation of social learning/observational learning (Bandura, 1977) and the disinhibition pathway: individuals acquire or abandon certain behavioral scripts by observing others' behaviors and their consequences. When subjects repeatedly witness perpetrators verbally abusing, assaulting, and raping victims without punishment in films, they may unconsciously lower internal inhibition and regard such behavior as acceptable or even imitable. This also helps explain why participants exhibited greater aggressiveness towards women after viewing two sexual violence films featuring distinctly different victim portrayals.

However, the data also show that the aggressiveness exhibited by participants after watching sexual violence content with a negative manifestation was slightly lower than that of those who viewed the positive portrayal version. In the questionnaire, participants rated the victim's 'suffering' highest and their 'responsibility attribution' lowest in the film depicting a negative manifestation; Conversely, in the positive portrayal version, participants generally perceived the victim as experiencing a greater degree of enjoyment and bearing more responsibility. That is to say, when the victim displays pain, disgust, and helplessness, the observer will, to some extent, mobilize empathy. Once the victim displays a pleasurable expression on screen, the audience tends to believe that 'she actually consents,' thereby psychologically facilitating the acceptance of violence against women.

However, regardless of whether the victim 'displays pleasure,' the perpetrator inflicts sexual violence to an equally severe degree in both videos, including beating, verbal abuse, and binding, all of which are present in both films. Audiences instinctively base their judgment of whether violence is present on the victim's subjective facial expressions: if you display pain, then you are being assaulted; if your expression is one of pleasure, it is assumed that you are enjoying it. This standard of judgment closely parallels the defense arguments of perpetrators in actual rape cases—'Because she also experienced orgasm, she was therefore willing to be assaulted by me.' The former internalizes 'orgasm = consensual sexual activity' within themselves, while adult pornography internalizes 'being sexually assaulted = enjoyment' within the minds of audiences; there is little difference between the two.

In response to a possible counterargument—that the strong aggressive behavior observed

in Experiment 1 occurred only under the anger condition, and thus sexual violence content simply functioned as a 'catalyst' in a specific context—the researchers introduced a 'No anger' group in Experiment 2 and replaced all experiment assistants with females to enable comparison with the 'Anger' group. The experimental procedure was largely consistent with the previous one, except that the 'No anger' group received positive feedback rather than punishment following the writing task. The results of Experiment 2 indicated that the 'No anger' group exhibited smaller and significantly lower increases in female-directed aggressiveness after viewing 'neutral,' 'non-violent erotic,' and 'sexual violence (negative manifestation)' films relative to the 'Anger' group; However, following exposure to 'sexual violence (positive portrayal),' their aggressiveness toward women increased significantly, remaining only slightly below that of the 'aggravated group.'

Therefore, based on this study's findings, we can cautiously infer that audiences consuming pornography depicting sexual violence with victims' positive responses in daily life exhibit an emotional state closer to the experimental 'non-aggravated group,' yet they may still demonstrate a stronger propensity for aggression toward real women after viewing, and cognitively, are more likely to accept the justification of sexual assault under certain conditions.

This 1981 study on pornography consumption is significant not only because it verified that viewing sexually violent content increases viewers' aggressiveness in the short term, particularly directed toward a specific gender, but also because it specifically examined the portrayal of women 'enjoying' sexual violence content, revealing how the glorification of sexual violence in mainstream pornography distorts individual cognition. The critical issue is that when individuals assess the severity of rape solely based on the victim's expressed feelings (such as enjoyment or crying) rather than the rape act itself and the objective extent of violence, responsibility shifts from the perpetrator to the victim, giving rise to narratives such as 'if you were raped, you should show distress' or 'she enjoyed it, so it was not rape,' which amount to victim blaming. In other words, sexual violence videos overwrite individuals' cognition by repeatedly enacting the script logic in viewers' minds that 'women can experience pleasure regardless of consent,' thereby shifting the evaluation of sexual violence from the act itself to the victim's response.

This aestheticized portrayal of sexual violence, over time, gradually associates sexual violence with female pleasure; Although it never depicts objective reality, it objectively becomes the execution script within the individual's cognition. As shown in experiments, after viewing, subjects are more inclined in the short term to attribute greater responsibility for the incident to women who display enjoyment of sexual violence; consequently, although the perpetrator's violent behavior remains unchanged, their responsibility is relatively diminished. If an individual repeatedly views such works, linking 'sexual violence with enjoyment' and internalizing the cognition that 'because women display pleasure, the perpetrator's responsibility is reduced and

the severity of the incident is diminished,' would he, under this logic, be more inclined to commit sexual violence?

1.4.2 The Relationship Between Viewing Violent Pornography and Perpetrating Sexual Violence

This issue is not unfounded. An empirical study of Dutch university students (n=686) demonstrated that exposure to violent pornography increases the risk of sexually violent behavior. Researchers measured respondents' perpetration of sexual violence as well as their consumption of violent pornography (frequency and type). Within the male sample, a positive correlation was identified between the extent of violent pornography consumption and the degree of sexually violent behavior: the more frequently violent pornography was viewed, the greater the reported likelihood of having perpetrated sexual violence (de Roos & Ferrando, 2025).

Moreover, the stronger an individual's perception of pornography as realistic (i.e., the degree to which pornography is considered to 'reflect reality'), and the higher the acceptance of rape myths among peers, the more this situation is intensified. As previously discussed in sexual script theory, the pathways through which sexual behavior is constituted often rely on the 'perjury' of others' experiences, meaning that individuals construct their own executable sexual scripts by interpreting 'what others are experiencing.' From the variable of an individual's authentic perception of pornography, it can be further observed that pornographic materials, as realistic substitutes for interpersonal scripts, constitute a highly accessible pathway for the acquisition of sexual scripts. The so-called 'authenticity' here does not refer to the formal accuracy of behavioral depiction, but rather to the ease with which individuals incorporate such content into their own sexual scripts. Reflected in Hentai works, although these do not belong to the category of live-action pornography, they can nonetheless, through realistic character depictions and exaggerated behavioral scenarios, cause certain individuals to regard them on the level of sexual scripts as metaphors and reflections of actual gender relations and sexual behaviors.

Research further indicates that, compared to females, surveyed males hold more positive attitudes toward pornographic content, demonstrate higher viewing frequency, and prefer more extreme themes. By linking this to peer-based high acceptance of rape myths that exacerbate sexually violent behavior, we can establish a simplified community-level model of intensified sexual violence: within online Hentai viewing communities, individuals discuss with others in comment sections and similar spaces, collectively constructing an identification with the male protagonists' behaviors portrayed in the works. Through this 'collective viewing,' they enact the moral disengagement described by Bandura, diffusing cognitive responsibility throughout the community's influence, thereby lowering the moral condemnation threshold for

violent scripts and facilitating greater identification with the commission of sexually violent behaviors. Consequently, a phenomenon emerges in which a community-wide high acceptance of rape myths influences the occurrence of individual sexually violent behavior, thereby aligning with the findings of experimental research. The distinction from the experiment lies in the fact that this 'peer' influence is transferred to an anonymous online environment, where discourse can be more uninhibited and extreme, rendering it more alarming.

1.4.3 The Causal Relationship Between Acceptance of Rape Myths and Propensity for Sexual Offending

In numerous studies concerning pornography, the measurement of acceptance of rape myths is a prevalent methodology, and extensive research findings have been obtained. However, the concept of rape myths, which has been consistently emphasized, still appears insufficiently intuitive to most opponents of pornography; it lacks the strength to adequately explain the impact of viewing extreme pornography. In the foregoing text, we have already demonstrated that rape myths serve as a complete mediation in the relationship between individuals' consumption of adult animation and the implementation of sexual assault strategies. Nevertheless, this remains inadequate; as we have noted, most longitudinal studies on pornography examine only the short-term effects of viewing pornographic content, while cross-sectional studies of viewers face challenges in directly and clearly establishing a behavioral trajectory from viewing to perpetrating crime. In this context, a longitudinal study examining the acceptance of rape myths and rape proclivity over an extended period is particularly important.

In a study conducted at the University of Central Florida, researchers centered their investigation on whether a bidirectional causal relationship exists between rape myths and rape proclivity. The sample comprised 488 male university students ($n=488$) from a public university. The study spanned several months and involved four rounds of questionnaire follow-ups conducted over nearly one year, at four time points from freshman enrollment to the beginning of sophomore year (T1, T2, T3, T4). At each interval, participants' acceptance of rape myths and rape proclivity were repeatedly measured. Acceptance of rape myths was assessed using the Revised Illinois Rape Myth Acceptance Scale, while rape proclivity was measured through two classical hypothetical questions: 'If you were certain no one would know and you would not be punished, how likely would you be to force someone unwilling to have sex?' and 'Under the same conditions, how likely would you be to engage in sex with someone too intoxicated to refuse?' Participants rated these items on a scale from 1 to 5, from which a 'rape enactment proclivity' index was derived. The analytical approach employed structural equation modeling and cross-lagged panel models (O'Connor, 2021).

The study found that the autoregressive coefficients for acceptance of rape myths and rape proclivity ranged approximately from 0.35–0.40 and 0.34–0.38, respectively, indicating that both acceptance of rape myths and rape proclivity represent relatively stable cognitive constructs rather than short-term emotional fluctuations. For instance, if an individual exhibited a high acceptance of rape myths one year earlier, it is highly likely that this acceptance would persist over the subsequent year; the same applies to rape proclivity (O'Connor, 2021).

It demonstrates that the acceptance of rape myths remains persistently high over the long term rather than naturally decreasing; however, this does not imply that acceptance of rape myths is unaffected by external factors. Research shows that variables increasing acceptance of rape myths may include perceived peer attitudes and the strength of patriarchy within cultural structures; however, most studies examining these factors are immediate and short-term. Longitudinally, repeated exposure to media depicting sexual violence (such as films portraying sexual violence) is associated with a significant and sustained increase in acceptance of rape myths. For instance, Vangeel, L., Eggermont, S., and Vandenbosch, L. demonstrated in a six-year longitudinal study that adolescents who watch music television featuring pronounced sexual objectification of women tend to develop heightened 'gender role perceptions,' which subsequently increase acceptance of rape myths in early adulthood. This indicates that, although RMA represents a relatively stable attitudinal structure in this experiment, it remains subject to change under ongoing stimulation from the socio-cultural environment.

Moreover, limited studies focusing on university populations with high acceptance of rape myths show that short-term prevention programs on campus significantly reduce rape proclivity and acceptance of rape myths among low-risk males but are ineffective for high-risk males (Elias-Lambert & Black, 2015). Conversely, it may produce a 'boomerang effect' on the individual, whereby exposure to information opposing sexual violence norms may instead intensify their perpetration behavior (Bosson et al., 2019; Bosson et al., 2015; Malamuth et al., 2018).

When applied to the consumption of adult animation, this suggests that merely issuing superficial warnings or restrictions on sexual violence content—such as labeling OVA discs of adult animation as harmful content and displaying slogans like 'Do not emulate in real life'—may be ineffective for long-term Hentai enthusiasts. In fact, it may exacerbate their psychological reactance toward consuming sexual violence content, thereby potentially leading to sexual crimes. Such slogans by animation companies are no more than self-deception. According to our theoretical framework, such extreme themes should not be regarded as harmless virtual content but rather as scripts and fantasy rehearsals for individuals to engage in sexual crimes. **Unless the depiction of sexual crimes in adult animation is fundamentally regulated through thematic restrictions and prohibitions,** any governance efforts concerning adult animation will amount to a mere drop in the bucket.

The central findings of this research indicate a clear bidirectional causal relationship between acceptance of rape myths and rape proclivity, **with rape proclivity during time periods T1 and T3 predicting subsequent acceptance of rape myths at T2 and T4, and standardized coefficients approximately ranging from 0.16 to 0.24. Similarly, acceptance of rape myths can predict subsequent rape proclivity; for instance, acceptance of rape myths at T2 predicts rape proclivity at T3, with a standardized coefficient of approximately 0.27, which is statistically significant. That is, within this cohort, individuals with a high acceptance of rape myths are more likely to exhibit elevated rape proclivity in the future; Furthermore, individuals who manifest high rape proclivity at earlier stages are also more likely to exhibit greater acceptance of rape myths in subsequent assessments, thereby forming a mutually reinforcing feedback loop** (O'Connor, 2021).

Therefore, we can derive a simplified logical chain:

Acceptance of rape myths ↑ ← bidirectional causal relationship → Rape proclivity ↑

Within this chain, if variables that contribute to an increased acceptance of rape myths are included, it can form a preliminary and complete logical chain from viewing to cognitive implementation. However, based on existing research findings, we can only speculate that prolonged and repeated viewing of adult animation may increase acceptance of rape myths, thereby elevating rape proclivity, eventually leading to the commission of actual crimes.

Moreover, an additional experiment conducted at the University of California confirmed that short-term exposure to R-rated films featuring pornographic violence reduces empathy toward victims of domestic violence.

The experiment involved 108 participants (n=108), all of whom were male university students. The procedure consisted of two stages: initially, participants viewed horror films depicting sexual violence three times over one week, during which their emotional responses and evaluations of the films were assessed; subsequently, at 3, 5, and 7 days post-viewing, participants watched documentary interviews of actual domestic violence victims and then assessed their own empathy levels as well as the severity of the victims' injuries. In Phase One, participants reported lower negative physiological arousal on the third day and provided lower evaluations of the explicitness and severity of sexual violence depicted in the film, indicating the completion of cognitive desensitization to sexual violence content. In Phase Two, three days post-viewing, subjects who had watched a domestic violence documentary exhibited significantly reduced empathy toward female domestic violence victims on self-report measures, alongside significantly lower ratings of the severity of harm. However, all subjects subsequently returned to baseline levels within a few days, demonstrating cognitive resensitization (Mullin & Linz, 1995).

From the experiments, it can be observed that viewing R-rated films containing sexually violent content may result in short-term cognitive desensitization to sexual violence, accompanied by a decreased level of sympathy for female victims and a diminished recognition of the severity of their injuries. In real-world application, we can indirectly infer that viewing sexually violent content may significantly reduce both the sympathy toward rape victims and the recognition of the harm they endure.

Through detailed analysis of these studies, we have demonstrated that viewing sexually violent content induces short-term moral inhibition in individuals, thereby justifying aggression against women, attenuating sympathy for female victims, influencing the perception of victimization severity, and further discussing the association between viewing violent pornography and the commission of sexual violence. Evidently, although these studies focus on live-action pornography, they are equally insightful and explanatory for the consumption of animated pornography, because live-action and animated pornography fundamentally share an intrinsic logical framework, ultimately aimed at the domination of women.

Summary

By referencing the limited empirical research on Hentai, we have connected a logical chain that aligns with the 'sexual scripts' in our theoretical framework from two perspectives: that 'viewing Hentai may be more dangerous than viewing live-action pornography' and that 'viewing Hentai does not diminish cognition regarding real women (attractiveness, romantic propensity).' Meanwhile, we attempt through this perspective to connect a limited number of Hentai research findings with the relatively numerous conclusions from live-action pornography studies, thereby constructing a preliminary analytical framework for the cognitive impact of viewing Hentai on individuals. This framework aims to demonstrate the difficulty of upholding the proposition of 'virtual harmlessness' in light of existing evidence and to refute the claim that viewing extreme Hentai works constitutes merely 'harmless entertainment.' Even though, in principle, no real women are harmed during the production of Hentai, its influence can still propagate through repeated viewing, reinforcing the prevailing gender order and logic of domination in reality.

This research essay indicates that animated pornography (Hentai) is far from a 'harmless fantasy projection'; rather, it can be empirically observed to exert cognitive impacts across multiple dimensions comparable to those caused by live-action pornography. It must be reiterated that anime, as a mode of expression, merely serves as a medium of communication and is not inherently problematic. What truly warrants critical attention is the industrial framework and transactional logic that, cloaked in the form of anime, presents extreme fantasies and commodifies depictions of violent crimes against women; this represents an extreme form of sexual commodification.

Precisely because individuals regard anime content as virtual fantasy, depictions of domination and crime may appear explicit, disturbing, and abhorrent. Therefore, it is necessary to systematically re-examine the pornographic content represented by Hentai and ACG culture. However, it remains premature to reach definitive conclusions; criticism and regulation of Hentai must continue to be supported and refined through rigorous empirical research.

Innocent Fantasy? How Viewing Perpetuates Sexual Crime

2.1 Dark figures in sexual assault cases

Prior to formally engaging with this chapter, it is essential to acknowledge that severe dark figures exist within the domain of sexual assault cases. The so-called dark figures of crime refer to crime statistics that are not effectively captured in official records. For example, if a customer steals candy from a supermarket but the store owner does not detect it, this objectively constitutes a theft case that goes unreported; such a case should be included within the dark figures of crime.

Data confirm that dark figures of sexual assault against women are widespread in certain countries. For example, an official 2006 report from England and Wales indicated that 13,780 rape cases were reported that year [98]. However, according to a 2013 joint survey by the UK Ministry of Justice (MoJ), the Office for National Statistics (ONS), and the Home Office, only approximately 15% of women chose to report these incidents [99], implying that aside from the reported 13,780 cases (about 15%), there are roughly 78,000 cases, representing approximately 85%, that remain unrecorded in official statistics. Excluding defamation cases, the total number of rape incidents in 2006 can be estimated at approximately 90,000 for that year.

Beyond the evident low reporting rate, rape adjudications demonstrate an exceptionally low conviction rate; a 2005 study revealed that only 5.7% of perpetrators in reported rape cases were convicted [100]. Thus, of the 13,000 reported rape cases, only about 650 were likely successfully prosecuted. This low conviction rate is interrelated with the aforementioned low reporting rate: the low reporting rate intensifies the low conviction rate, while the low conviction rate leads more women to believe that perpetrators will not be punished even if cases enter the judicial system, thereby diminishing the likelihood of reporting. Even in Iceland, renowned as a 'female paradise,' nearly one-quarter of females have experienced rape and sexual assault, with nearly half self-reporting having suffered sexual violence.

This is not a situation unique to any single country. A sampling survey covering six Asian countries and nine regions reveals that approximately one-quarter of males report having committed at least one act of coerced sex against females during their lifetime; in certain

regions, this figure reaches as high as 62% (Fulu et al., 2013). These figures are alarming; the high rates largely result from the 'anonymous self-administered questionnaire combined with audio assistance' methodology, which diminishes respondents' shame and alleviates their apprehension during completion, thus providing more accurate data (Fulu et al., 2013). Thus, it reveals a more realistic and explicit base rate of sexual crimes before our eyes.

The fundamental purpose of the global #MeToo movement is to give a voice to the sexual assaults experienced by marginalized women and women of color [101]. Its original initiator, social activist Tarana Burke, was inspired to use the phrase "Me Too" after witnessing a 13-year-old girl who had been sexually assaulted and unsure of how to respond [102]. This later developed into a worldwide social movement. The phrase "Me too" signifies empathy and care from those who have experienced similar situations; it embodies the conviction that "you are not alone" and the encouragement that "we stand with you." It empowers victims to courageously come forward and accuse their former perpetrators, compelling both the wider public and previously indifferent politicians to confront this serious and widespread problem affecting women. It can be asserted that the #MeToo movement itself has, for the first time on a large scale, brought to light the countless silenced cries, moans, helplessness, and confusion within sexual violence and sexual assault against women, as well as the substantial dark figures accumulating beyond official statistics.

These factors collectively demonstrate that data on sexual crimes against women far exceed the statistics reported by governmental authorities; behind those cold numerical reports lies an incalculable number of victims and perpetrators who remain at large. This inevitably generates uncertainty in estimating the true scale of such crimes. In the context of viewing adult animation, Hentai proponents citing so-called 'official data' to claim that viewing Hentai pornography is harmless no longer possess absolute persuasive authority, as the actual scale of sexual crime perpetrators is likely far greater than the public's habitual perception of a 'very small number of offenders.'

2.2 Rape Is Not an Isolated Incident

Rape is not merely a singular, incidental sexual crime; rather, it constitutes an extreme result arising from the gradual accumulation of experiences, spanning from the emergence of sexual fantasy to the commission of sexual harassment.

This is a somewhat counterintuitive conclusion. For example, a report published by the UK Ministry of Justice indicated that the majority of individuals in the sample convicted of serious sexual assault (serious sexual assault) had no prior sexual crime records, with only about 30% having previous sexual offense convictions (Howard et al., 2023). This appears to directly challenge our conclusion; however, it is important to remember that the report relies on official records, and thus its scope is limited exclusively to official statistics. In the domain of sexual

crime, which may involve substantial underreporting and dark figures, official statistics occasionally fail to fully represent the actual situation.

Sexual harassment is defined in General Recommendation No. 19 of the United Nations Committee on the Elimination of Discrimination against Women as “ an unwelcome conduct of a sexual nature, such as physical contact and proximity, sexually motivated comments, or demands related to pornography and sexuality expressed verbally or through conduct ” (Committee on the Elimination of Discrimination against Women, 1992). It can be classified by behavior into verbal sexual harassment, physical sexual harassment, and environmental sexual harassment [103]. As a form of sexual offense, sexual harassment, due to its high incidence in transient locations and the diversity of its criminal manifestations, creates a situation wherein even when reports are filed, the police face significant difficulties in initiating investigations.

At the same time, sexual harassment frequently receives insufficient attention at the social level, further diminishing victims' likelihood of reporting after experiencing such behavior, thereby resulting in substantial dark figures. A nationwide survey conducted in Spain in 2019 found that among victims of non-intimate partner sexual violence—including rape and threats—approximately 8% personally reported the incidents to the police or courts, whereas the reporting rate among sexual harassment victims was only about 2.5% (Delegación del Gobierno contra la Violencia de Género, 2020). Compared to non-intimate partner sexual violence, which includes rape and indecency, the rate of police reporting for sexual harassment is significantly lower.

This indirectly indicates that the proportion of reported sexual harassment cases is far smaller than that of rape, while the overall incidence is substantially greater than that of rape. For instance, a summary analysis by the UK Home Office in the late 2000s estimated that approximately 100,000 people (both males and females) experience rape or penetrative sexual assault annually (Ministry of Justice, Home Office, & Office for National Statistics, 2013), whereas UK police recorded roughly 12,000 to 14,000 rape cases per year in the mid-2000s (Ministry of Justice, 2009). Furthermore, this Home Office report estimated that annually over 470,000 females and males experience some form of sexual crime (Ministry of Justice, Home Office, & Office for National Statistics, 2013), implying that sexual harassment accounts for a considerable share of these incidents. Apart from approximately 100,000 individuals subjected to rape or penetrative sexual assault, an additional 370,000 victims experience other forms of sexual crime. Moreover, within UK law enforcement, 'sexual harassment' is not recognized as a standalone offense but is subdivided into more specific categories such as 'sexual assault' and 'stalking and harassment.' Instances of verbal harassment are addressed only through civil procedures, complicating victims' capacity to assess their legal position when encountering sexual harassment. Thus, statistical data reveal cases where individuals are convicted of severe sexual assault despite lacking prior criminal records. Irrespective of interpretative frameworks,

these dark figures undeniably exist, representing a substantially larger scale and constituting a significant criminal incubator that facilitates the commission of rape in practice.

The study by de Roos and Ferrando (2025) demonstrates that individuals who self-report having committed rape are often also the primary perpetrators within less severe categories of offending; the overlap between these more severe and less severe offending behaviors indicates a continuity of sexual offending in certain individuals. Liz Kelly conceptualizes various types of sexual crime as interconnected elements within a single structural framework, rather than categorizing them dichotomously by severity; Accordingly, she introduced the concept of the 'continuum of sexual violence' to articulate the structural continuity of sexually violent behaviors, ranging from harassment and indecency to rape. Whether unsolicited verbal harassment or rape acts imposed through power, these should not be regarded as separate pathways of sexual crime merely because of differing severity; rather, they ought to be understood as points on a progressively emerging spectrum from the bottom up: at the individual level, rape and sexual harassment are simply different nodes along the same continuum.

Kavanaugh et al., through in-depth interviews with young women participating in nightlife, found that a single woman repeatedly encountered a range of behaviors within the same context, from verbal harassment and physical contact to forced kissing, forced hugging, and sexual assault while intoxicated. This process is not regarded as a completely independent event in the article's narrative but is presented as a chain of events demonstrating a progressively escalating severity with cumulative intensification (Kavanaugh, 2013). In other words, harassment, indecency, and rape are not isolated incidents but interconnected nodes within a mutually reinforcing and influencing chain.

From a longitudinal perspective, the concrete manifestation of this pathway varies among individuals: some may remain at the level of sexual crime fantasy throughout their lives, never having the opportunity or willingness to enact it in reality; others, while concurrently developing extreme sexual fantasies, begin to engage in behaviors such as sexual harassment and indecency, progressively moving upward along this path—either stagnating due to increased risks and costs or ultimately reaching the pinnacle, resulting in the occurrence of severe sexual assault.

From this, it can be observed that beyond the mere outcome of sexual offending, the sexual offending behaviors of individual perpetrators also demonstrate structural continuity and staged progression: some ultimately remain at the foundational level of sexual crime fantasy, others linger at the stage of physical harassment, while some individuals, through gradual desensitization, proceed to commit rape. The critical point is that among perpetrators a correlation exists in sexual offending behaviors: rapists and train molesters (chikan) are not

entirely independent but can often be considered as sequential manifestations along the same criminal trajectory—however, this does not imply that all train molesters inevitably 'progress' to become rapists; their developmental trajectory depends considerably on various factors, including peer attitudes and the deterrent effect of legal sanctions.

Overall, this trajectory represents a gradual process of internalizing attitudes and scripts related to sexual assault, which subsequently materializes as actual sexual assault behaviors: it may begin as mere sexual fantasy, evolve into acceptance of seemingly 'minor' sexual harassment, and under particular circumstances escalate further to desires for and attempts at indecency and rape. In brief, sexually violent behavior in many individuals follows a progressively escalating trajectory. Given the enormous dark figures of crime estimated by the UK Home Office cited above, this is hardly surprising.

Simultaneously, such scripts may be continuously shaped by the external environment and are also subject to ongoing contestation and negotiation within the individual's internal psyche; due to external influences, not all of these necessarily manifest in reality. However, once the cognitive process of recognizing a sexual assault fantasy is complete, the individual is already situated within the potential population of sexual offenders and, under specific circumstances, may be driven to commit the act through 'holes' in regulation and norms. This is the concept I am about to develop next—I term it the 'Swiss-cheese × Pyramid' sexual offense risk model. If, on the one hand, there exists a vast and indeterminable dark figure of social crime at the macro level, and on the other hand, sexual criminal behaviors are not isolated, independent phenomena, then can we construct a model to elucidate how the risk of sexual crime escalates along this trajectory and is integrated into the risk structure of wider society?

2.3 The Network of Norms and Regulation

Firstly, the inspiration for my model derives from an early, somewhat radical personal view—that for certain consumers of extreme pornography, what truly restrains them is often not inherent morality but rather legal and social deterrents. The meaning of this sentence is straightforward. Although consumers today do not commit sexual offenses as a result of viewing depictions of extreme sexual violence, this does not imply that extreme pornography is harmless. Much of the deterrence derives from law and authority. Furthermore, this deterrence does not require law to undertake substantive action to be effective, as it implicitly disciplines individuals to continuously comply with social norms, maintaining constant self-surveillance. Consequently, once an individual departs from normative order, punishment ensues automatically without the need for external enforcement.

However, it is evident that although such external and self-imposed constraints are effective in most cases, reality shows that a significant portion of individuals can overcome this deterrence under certain circumstances and remove self-restraint to commit sexual crimes. We

often say 'Heaven's net is vast and wide,' but since the law is a 'net,' there must inevitably be gaps that individuals can exploit. From this standpoint, we can hypothesize the existence of a net between individuals who generate sexual offender fantasies and those who commit sexual offenses. Individuals who develop sexual offender fantasies can be shaped by multiple factors; however, our theory focuses specifically on the consumer group that internalizes sexual scripts through viewing extreme depictions in adult animation.

Within this rough binary of non-crime/crime, the web represents social 'Norms' and 'Regulation'; 'Norms' can be examined from the cultural dimension, representing society's attitude toward sexual offenders, whereas 'Regulation' refers to the practical supervision of sexual offenders. From the cultural dimension of 'Norms,' whether it is society's negative perception of sexual assault perpetrators or the association of such acts with erroneous moral values, both can serve as interventions against individuals inclined to commit sexual assault, and can also be internalized as individuals' self-regulation.

However, when constructs such as 'victim blaming,' the 'seducer theory,' and various rape myths emerge within society, shifting moral criticism onto victims who have experienced sexual assault, this may, conversely, exacerbate individuals' beliefs in perpetrating sexual assault. This occurs because societal values are similarly internalized by the individual. 'When a lie is repeated a thousand times, it becomes truth.' When individuals within society internalize this logic of condemning victims, it becomes an implicit consensus whereby responsibility is diffused onto victims, allowing perpetrators to achieve moral exoneration. This constitutes a cognitive gap at the cultural dimension. Furthermore, if the cognition that adopts a positive attitude toward sexual crime becomes increasingly prevalent, the gaps in the network preventing crime will widen, leading individuals to cognitively accept sexual crime.

At the practical level, supervision of sexual assault—including legally mandated measures to promote the prevention and punishment of sexual assault and authoritative deterrence of individuals—is exemplified by recent reforms to sexual crime legislation in Japan, which replaced the 'crime of rape' emphasizing violence and coercion with the 'crime of non-consensual intercourse' [105]. Similarly, the United Kingdom's amendment prohibiting 'upskirting' [106] represents official regulatory efforts undertaken by various countries. However, at the level of policy implementation, there remains a considerable gap between reality and ideal; there are still societal corners beyond the reach of authoritative regulation. These areas create gaps through which individuals commit crimes. As authority becomes increasingly passive in governance, these gaps expand, allowing more individuals to circumvent preventive measures and perpetrate crimes. Moreover, unlike prior cognition, legal regulation alone cannot address all issues. The governance of sexual crime necessitates coordinated efforts with cultural dimension guidance, making this inherently a prolonged process.

2.4 A Reexamination of the Swiss Cheese Model

But is the reality of the world simply a binary division between 'crime' and 'no crime'? To further elaborate on this model, we may refer to the Swiss Cheese Model, first proposed by Professor James Reason from the University of Manchester in 1990. This model draws inspiration from the naturally occurring holes in Swiss cheese during its fermentation process; when a single slice of cheese is held up to a light source, light can pass through its holes and penetrate the cheese; however, when multiple slices of cheese are stacked, the differing positions of the holes in each slice obstruct the passage of light. However, in extreme cases, if the holes in consecutive slices of cheese align, light can pass through.

Light is conceptualized as the occurrence of a hazard (termed by Reason as 'a trajectory of accident opportunity'), and the holes in the slices of cheese represent weaknesses in multilayered system defenses; when these holes briefly align and the vulnerabilities coincide, the hazard can penetrate all layers, resulting in an accident (Reason, 1990). This theory has been extensively applied to risk analysis and control in accident prevention across domains such as aviation safety and computer security.

Swiss Cheese Model schematic diagram (source: Wikipedia [107])

However, within the existing literature, few have attempted to extend this model to the

social level of sexual offenders; originally developed for 'industrial accidents/medical errors,' the model similarly offers heuristic value and warrants discussion when applied to the macro-social context of sexual assault risk. Through rigorous empirical research analysis, it is understood that severe sexual assault can be conceptualized as a progressive layering of sexual offense behaviors. In the simplified 'net' and 'holes' model, we identify that the key to preventing sexual assault depends on cultural norms and authoritative regulation, which together form an intercepting net targeting potential perpetrators with criminal tendencies. The gaps in this net signify failures in authoritative regulation and incompleteness within cultural norms.

At the macro-social level, through the analysis of dark figures of crime, it becomes evident that the channels—namely, the widespread existence of gaps leading to sexual crimes—within the current social order are observable, although the exact figures can only be estimated. This aligns with the holes in the Swiss Cheese Model, where 'norms' and 'supervision' collectively form defensive barriers against sexual crimes; it is clear that these barriers inevitably contain holes, which are widespread due to the substantial presence of dark figures.

While sexual crime at the micro level is not an inevitable consequence produced by any single individual, at the macro-social level it manifests as an observable probabilistic increase. Furthermore, the occurrence of sexual crimes results from the simultaneous failure of multiple preventive mechanisms across social structures, reflected at the individual level. From an enforcement perspective, ineffective police patrols at night and the absence of preventive warnings in public spaces may constitute some of the factors contributing to sexual assault. Tracing back to the root, the failure to implement timely cognitive interventions and guidance is a significant factor in the transformation of an individual into a 'potential individual' who may commit crimes through 'holes,' such as platforms ignoring and permitting the unchecked dissemination of extreme hate speech, extreme pornography, and sexual violence content, which ultimately can lead to desensitization toward sexual assault and encourage criminal tendencies. This is not about assigning blame to any individual but rather about elucidating how this structural mechanism operates and the degree to which it shapes the risk environment for sexual offenders, which is precisely the analytical focus I intend to highlight.

Reason, in his paper 'Human Error: Models and Management,' distinguishes human error into two categories: the 'person approach' and the 'system approach.' The 'person approach' emphasizes separation from system structures, focusing more on the individual; when an error occurs, it is attributed to individual fault, thereby attempting to decouple responsibility from the relevant institutions as much as possible. In contrast, the 'system approach' adopts a broader, holistic perspective, emphasizing that individual errors are inevitable. 'Error' is the result rather than the cause, rooted in various systemic factors. It focuses on how defense mechanisms at different systemic levels function and why they fail when an accident occurs (Reason, 2000).

Correspondingly, my argument in this paper emphasizes that the structural problem of sexual assault should be understood as the joint effect of the gender system, culture, and market; the source of risk is not an individual's sudden eruption of 'bestial nature,' but rather the continually learned, reinforced, and cyclically reproduced sexual scripts behind it.

2.5 The Swiss Cheese × Pyramid Sexual Offense Risk Model

2.5.1 The layered model from L0–L3 — from attitudes and fantasies to rape

Building on the aforementioned macro framework, it is necessary to further specify the behavioral distribution of 'sexual assault'; previous analyses of the Swiss Cheese Model primarily focused on hazards and accidents as the initial and terminal points. In our theoretical framework, this model must be further stratified. We note that an individual's sexual offending behavior can escalate incrementally from minor to severe acts. Although this pattern is not predominant in official records, a reasonable explanation is that minor sexual offenses by individuals often go unrecorded by authorities, a point we have underscored repeatedly above. Thus, in our macro-level social model, the gradual escalation of individual sexual offending should be explicitly reflected. If hazards are considered 'potential perpetrators' exhibiting a high propensity for sexual assault and strongly held rape myths, then the losses arising from their penetration through layered cheese holes can be categorized into three levels, namely:

L1 = verbal harassment, non-contact harassment. With reference to the Convention on the Elimination of All Forms of Discrimination Against Women (CEDAW) General Recommendation No. 19, and the International Labour Organization (ILO) Convention on Violence and Harassment for the definition of sexual harassment [108], this category includes unwelcome and unacceptable verbal harassment with sexual connotations (such as sexual teasing, sexual degradation, and sexualization comments), as well as non-contact harassment involving the display of pornographic content, exposure of one's own genitalia or sexually suggestive gestures, and voyeuristic observation of others' bodies or private acts. Such behaviors are frequently perceived as relatively mild and are often disregarded within existing legal frameworks and social discourse.

L2 = Physical harassment, sexual coercion. Compared to verbal harassment and non-contact harassment, physical harassment and sexual contact are regarded as more severe in many current laws and policy discourses; for example, the World Health Organization (WHO) explicitly classifies 'unwelcome sexual contact' as a form of sexual violence (sexual violence) [109]. According to statements from local governments and legal teams, such behavior typically includes unwelcome kissing, hugging, touching, deliberate pressing against the body, and slapping of the buttocks [110][111]. Sexual coercion denotes non-consensual sexual activities achieved through non-physical and non-violent means, including fraud, threats, and the

exploitation of personal influence and authority. Distinguished from L3, in this tier it exclusively refers to acts compelling others to accept fondling, touching of intimate body parts, indecency, and other non-penetrative sexual contact.

²L3 = Rape, non-consensual sexual intercourse. This tier constitutes the apex of sexual crimes. Referring to the British Crime Survey (BCS) analytical report, which unifies legally defined non-consensual penile vaginal penetration (rape) and acts involving penile or other body parts or objects penetrating the vagina or anus with sexual intent (penetrative sexual assault) under the concept of 'severe sexual assault' [112], as well as the description in Japan's 2023 amended Crime of Non-Consensual Intercourse statute [113], this tier includes non-consensual sexual intercourse, oral sex, anal sex, and other such acts. Broadly, any non-consensual intrusion of the vagina, anus, or oral cavity—whether effected by a penis, other body parts, or objects—is encompassed within this level.

However, I must clarify that the grading conducted by this model aligns with the broad legal definitions of sexual crimes for the purpose of classification, and does not represent the severity of impact on victims in reality. In real-life contexts, for example, within the L1 layer, many actions such as the large-scale dissemination of private photos, even without reaching physical contact at the L2 level, can be as severe or even more detrimental than physical contact at the L2 layer. Regarding the L2 layer, although conduct such as physical harassment and indecency is legally less severe than penetrative sexual assault at the L3 layer, certain behaviors—for instance, prolonged indecency occurring in familiar settings such as schools or workplaces—may cause trauma to victims comparable to that of sexual assault at the L3 layer. The suffering experienced by victims should not be used for comparison or to determine who is more 'tragic'; for each individual involved, these experiences must be solemnly regarded as indelible trauma.

Furthermore, although the unilateral emergence of sexual assault fantasies, rape proclivity, and strong identification with violent sexual scripts do not constitute crimes, our analysis indicates that such individuals—considered 'potential perpetrators' as preconditions for criminal acts—are classified within the largest and most populous L0 layer.

L0 = Attitudes and fantasies. At this foundational level, attitudes include the cognitive justification of sexually violent behavior, the endorsement of rape myths, and a positive orientation toward belief structures that mitigate the perpetrator's responsibility while shifting blame onto the victim. Furthermore, aggressive sexual fantasies—centered on non-consensual acts such as domination, humiliation, coercion, and assault—are repeatedly amplified. Psychiatrist Zeng Qifeng, in his work **Fantasy as Reality**, argues that 'fantasy is the reality of

² Currently, the Crime Survey for England and Wales (CSEW)

the mind,' highlighting the profound influence of the unconscious on individual behavior [114]. Thus, fantasy is not innocuous but serves as a potential catalyst for actual behavior. In existing empirical research, such as a study conducted on a general German population sample (N=664), Bondü and Birke found that these types of fantasies demonstrate a robust positive correlation at the group level with sexual coercion and sexually violent behavior. Furthermore, these extreme sexual fantasies predict sexually aggressive behavior much more strongly than other traditional factors, with standardized regression coefficients exceeding 0.6 (Bondü & Birke, 2021).

Within sexual script theory, fantasy rehearsal constitutes a psychological script that sustains arousal through imagery and desire. As previously noted, individuals internalize extreme content viewed in Hentai through sexual scripts, and the key to this internalization lies in the continuous psychological process of fantasy. The L0 layer itself does not necessarily imply that an individual will proceed to commit crime; its function is to quantify individuals and incorporate them into the base population of potential 'perpetrators'. From the perspective of the Swiss Cheese Model, assuming the scale of defense holes remains constant, the larger the base population of individuals in L0, the greater the probability that individuals will pass through the holes and enter the L1, L2, and L3 layers. In other words, the number of 'potential perpetrators' at the L0 grassroots level is a key variable influencing the scale of crime at the upper strata.

After defining the four strata of L0, L1, L2, and L3, the next step is to construct the overall model. Firstly, it can be established that at the macro social level, the incidence of sexual crimes decreases progressively according to the severity presented in this paper. That is to say, individuals who endorse rape myths and sexual scripts are considerably more numerous than those who have actually committed verbal harassment and non-contact harassment; furthermore, this L1 layer of individuals is substantially larger than those who have engaged in physical harassment and sexual coercion.

This pattern arises because, based on previous experience, societal attention to various sexual crimes exhibits an unequal gradient, which is jointly determined by law and culture. As manifested within the grassroots 'potential individual,' sexual crimes are often categorized according to their severity. When an individual commits a relatively minor act, deterrence exerted by the authority stratum is perceived as comparatively minimal; conversely, when committing a relatively severe act, deterrence from the authority stratum is perceived as considerably greater. Within the structures of various strata, although this article regards the 'progressive escalation of behaviors' as a primary trajectory of sexual crime, this pathway is not necessarily completed by every victim. Conversely, we can conceive that in each stratum certain individuals are inevitably obstructed by the main body of the cheese, while a smaller proportion ascend through the holes, in a cyclical process. Therefore, the upward transition at each stratum is an event with a probability less than one; macroscopically, the number of participants necessarily contracts at each successive level from the bottom up. This model ultimately presents a formation analogous to the Pyramid of the ancient Egyptian pharaohs, with a relatively broad and inconspicuous base and a relatively sparse and conspicuous apex, as illustrated in the figure below:

Sexual Offending Risk Model: Pyramid × Swiss-Cheese Model

2.5.2 The Continuity and Transition of Sexual Violence from L0 to L3

Having conceptualized sexual crime as interrelated behaviors within the continuum of

sexual violence, this model regards sexual criminal behavior at the macroscopic social level as a progressively ascending chain, with sexual criminal acts across strata integrated to ultimately form a sophisticated Pyramid structure. Among them, the L0 layer, which comprises 'potential perpetrators' and represents the largest scale of pre-offender individuals who may transition into committing crimes, is a dynamic structure that can expand or contract in scale due to external factors. This layer is regarded as the starting point of sexual crime, where individuals reach the L1 layer through gaps in the 'slices of cheese' blocking them. This signifies that they have bypassed the omissions in 'norms' and 'supervision' to commit crimes. Such offenses are not necessarily captured by official statistics but undeniably exist at the social level. This framework is employed to reflect the substantial dark figures in actual sexual crimes; even when hidden statistically, the physical and psychological scars borne by victims remain indelible.

This model presupposes multiple possible pathways to approximate real-life situations as closely as possible. From a subjective experiential perspective, there can exist in reality a behavioral chain ascending from the L0 base layer to acts at L1, then gradually advancing through the holes in the L1 layer toward the L2 layer, and subsequently entering the apex L3 layer. This represents the progression of an individual who, after minor acts remain unchecked, incrementally commits increasingly severe criminal behaviors until reaching the apex of sexual violence escalation. It is an asymptotic path, which can be expressed as:

$$L0 \rightarrow L1 \rightarrow L2 \rightarrow L3$$

However, in practical terms, this idealized path is evidently not unique. For example, in some crime reports, individuals committing more severe sexual crimes may not have previously engaged in other forms of sexual harassment; alternatively, some individuals might not casually perpetrate verbal harassment in daily life but eventually commit physical harassment. These pathways are all plausible. This constitutes the logical chain of direct escalation manifested within the model. We hypothesize that the risk holes across various strata may temporarily align under specific circumstances, enabling individuals to bypass certain hierarchical levels and achieve transgression. For example, when the holes at the L0 layer and L1 layer align, a certain number of individuals at the grassroots can circumvent the criminal L1 layer and enter the L2 layer. In other words, when two barriers of differing defensive strength are both breached, the individual's criminal behavior exhibits level transgression. However, such behavioral level transgression does not imply cognitive level transgression. The model indicates that some individuals' cognition has already undergone a stepwise ascent; it merely appears, in behavior, as a sudden leap.

These paths are not merely theoretical conjectures but are, to some extent, corroborated by empirical research.

In a longitudinal study of American adolescents aged 13 to 25, researchers conducted four

rounds of data collection from online-recruited youth (n=1129) to perform latent class analysis on the clustering patterns of various forms of sexual violence (Ybarra et al., 2021). Sexual violence in this study was evaluated across six categories: sexual harassment, online sexual harassment, sexual assault, sexual coercion, attempted rape, and rape. The key findings of the study reveal that in each round of data collection, three stable sample groups consistently emerge: the non-perpetrator group, accounting for 69-81%; the sexual harassment group, accounting for 17-29%; and the multiple perpetrator group, accounting for 1-3%. With respect to behavioral escalation pathways, the proportion transitioning from the 'non-perpetrator' group to the 'sexual harassment' group is approximately 26%, while the proportion transitioning to the 'multiple perpetrator' group is 2% (Ybarra et al., 2021).

Data analysis indicates that these findings fundamentally correspond to the hypothesized pathway from 'potential individual' to the 'L1' level, providing empirical support for the hypothesis, with a transition rate that may be as high as approximately one quarter. Given that the sample collected in this study is relatively broad and may include both normal individuals with low tendencies toward sexual assault and rape myths as well as the 'potential perpetrators' in our model, it is reasonable to infer that excluding the non-'potential perpetrators' from the sample would result in a true conversion rate exceeding 26%. Regarding the 2% of individuals who transition into the "multiple perpetrator group," it can be inferred that they likely underwent a process of sequentially escalating behaviors from L0 to higher strata. Furthermore, if the "sexual harassment group" is used as a baseline and the "multiple perpetrator group" is considered as representing some individuals who ultimately reach the L3 layer, the conversion rate between these groups, while small, remains a figure that cannot be ignored. Therefore, after aligning the sample strata of this study with corresponding strata in our model:

The path L0 → L1 received partial support.

The path L0 → L1 → L2 → L3 is reflected in certain groups.

Following this is the ascending path from the L1 layer to the L2 layer. Our primary argument is that this path does indeed exist and can develop at scale. Compared to the path from L0 to L1, the ascent to L2 involves two types of individuals: some who advance after engaging in L1 behaviors, and others who leap directly from the grassroots. Examining the first traditional path, it represents the escalation of behavior following verbal harassment and non-contact harassment.

With the advancement of information technology, the issue of online sexual harassment has become increasingly severe, particularly acts such as sending obscene content to women and soliciting nude photographs. Additionally, non-contact sexual harassment, such as exposure, has become more brazen via the internet. These behaviors constitute illegal activities to varying degrees across countries. For instance, in China, under Article 42 of the Public

Security Administration Punishments Law of the People's Republic of China, individuals who repeatedly send obscene, insulting, intimidating, or other disruptive information may be detained for up to five days or fined up to 500 yuan; if the offense is serious, detention may extend beyond five days up to ten days, along with a fine not exceeding 500 yuan. Although China lacks specific legislation addressing acts such as exhibitionism, based on the treatment of individual cases, these acts can be prosecuted under charges of forced indecency or insult [115].

Online sexual harassment, as an extension of verbal harassment at the L1 layer, should not be evaluated solely based on the act itself, as it can also represent a key factor in the escalation of invasive behavior.

In a nationwide survey of American adolescents, researchers differentiated among various types of sexual violence, including 'sexualized online dating violence' and 'sexual coercion.' The results indicate that among adolescents who experienced sexualization-related online dating violence, more than half also reported victimization of sexual coercion—a proportion approximately several times that of adolescents who did not experience such online sexual violence (Zweig et al., 2013). This study demonstrates that the harm caused by online harassment behaviors not only exists intrinsically but also increases the likelihood of more severe behaviors in certain individuals. In this model, this can be regarded as an adolescent case example illustrating an escalation from verbal harassment at the L1 layer to sexual coercion at the L2 layer.

Regarding another form of crime at the L1 layer, the escalation pattern of non-contact harassment—primarily exemplified by exposure of genitals—can also receive partial support. A rapid evidence review published in 2024 by the UK College of Policing, summarizing research such as that by McNally and Fremouw (2014), indicates that among individuals already within the purview of the criminal justice or mental health systems due to sexual exposure, approximately 5%–10% subsequently engage in contact sexual crimes (College of Policing, 2024). In the application of this model, it demonstrates that escalation from non-contact harassment at the L1 layer to contact harassment at the L2 layer occurs in a small subset of individuals. Therefore, we identify two chains:

L1 Verbal harassment → L2 has received partial support

L1 Non-contact harassment → L2 has received partial support

Next, it escalates to L3, which is the most severe level; ascending to L3 signifies that the individual has committed rape and penetrative sexual acts against the victim. An extreme scenario, as reported in the news, is that an individual perceived as gentle and refined suddenly commits sexual assault on a particular night, seemingly without any warning. This phenomenon, as depicted in our model, suggests that a minority of individuals, after entering the L0

foundational level, may briefly align multiple defense holes at a critical moment and directly penetrate to L3.

However, this process is not entirely passive for the individual. To understand this chain, one can consider that the severity of individual circumstances varies within each stratum. Individuals who ascend directly from the L0 layer to L3 likely exhibit, even before committing a crime, more extreme and dangerous cognition of rape at the level of attitudes and fantasies. This raises a question: if such individuals exist within the L0 layer—as 'potential perpetrators' who have not yet committed a crime—how is it possible that they possess a dangerous cognition of sexual crime prior to offending, thereby actively turning toward crime when the opportunity arises?

At the level of sexual scripts, individuals internalize behaviors depicted in media containing sexual violence and sexual domination as preset behavioral scripts, which are further deepened and reinforced through continuous fantasy rehearsal. Over time, these may become consolidated as the individual's actual behavioral scripts. As previously discussed, aggressive sexual fantasies possess greater predictive power for sexual assault behaviors than other variables, such as exposure to violent pornography.

However, theoretically, viewing and fantasizing are not opposing phenomena; rather, they often represent successive stages. The emergence of an individual's aggressive sexual fantasies is by no means arbitrary but results from activation and shaping under the influence of external stimuli and cultural contexts. Upon reflection, for such individuals, sexual criminal behavior is not an entirely unfamiliar endeavor, but rather something that has been rehearsed innumerable times in their minds. Correspondingly, at the cognitive level, they have ascended to L1 and L2 repeatedly. In reality, when external situational holes arise, when the 'opportunity to actualize fantasy' occurs, L3 erupts manifestly in reality. This represents the potent force of fantasy within the risk trajectory of sexual violence.

Whereas the direct progression from L0 to L3 highlights the dangers of 'invisible fantasy,' the pathways ascending from the L1 and L2 layers emphasize how an individual, after engaging in relatively minor acts, continuously probes boundaries and accumulates experience, progressively intensifying until culminating in severe sexual criminal behavior. This underscores a notion of 'visible continuity.' The aforementioned study by Ybarra et al. also demonstrates that various forms of sexually violent behavior cluster within the same small subset of the population (Ybarra et al., 2021).

In an evaluative study of male interpersonal violence (n = 1882), an investigation of 120 individuals meeting the legal definitions of rape and attempted rape found that most were habitual offenders who had committed multiple acts; among these habitual offenders, the average number of rape cases per person was 5.8, accompanied by other extensive

interpersonal violent behaviors, totaling 1,225 incidents (Lisak & Miller, 2002). This also implies that rape acts at the L3 layer in reality may be highly concentrated among a small group of “multiple offenders,” who often simultaneously engage in other extensive forms of sexual assault and violent behavior.

In the interpretation presented herein, it can be considered that a significant portion of individuals reach the L3 layer; this does not indicate a single act of “rape,” but rather repeated offenses at levels equivalent to L1 and L2 over an extended period during the escalation process. It can also be understood that a small group of individuals, upon reaching L3, continuously cycle through multiple layers equivalent to L1–L3 in perpetrating these acts. If an individual has already engaged in L3 behavior, their cognitive risk level remains at the L3 stratum within our model, and in most cases, it does not revert or diminish to a lower layer; thus, behavior can fluctuate between strata, demonstrating diversity.

In summary, these studies collectively indicate that rape acts often do not occur in isolation but are highly concentrated within a small subgroup of perpetrators who also engage in other forms of sexual assault and interpersonal violence. This concentration, on one hand, indirectly supports the high-risk pathway involving a direct leap from extreme cognition and fantasy at the L0 layer to the L3 layer; Conversely, this also indicates that in many individuals, the perpetration of acts at the L1 and L2 layers and the rape acts at the L3 layer constitute different stages within a single continuous chain. In summary, based on the existing evidence, we can indirectly support the following two chains:

L0 → L3

L1、L2 → L3

2.6 The Correlation between Hentai and the 'Potential Individual'

In retrospect, sexual violence resembles a cyclical and escalating pathway across different layers rather than isolated event points. After rigorously analyzing, validating, and integrating such pathways into the 'Swiss Cheese × Pyramid' social model, we return to the persistent question: how does viewing Hentai and extreme pornography affect individuals and contribute to sexual crime?

Although this issue has been addressed through numerous expert opinions and empirical studies over time, very few have integrated the individual's crime chain into a macro-level social perspective. The model developed in this paper aims to intuitively illustrate the actual interconnections among various seemingly unrelated behaviors, as well as the operational process by which individuals commit crimes within society. This is a dynamic model, with each stratum interlinked and indispensable. The practical implication of this model is that governance of sexual crime cannot focus solely on prevention and control at the L3 stratum;

attention to the L1 and L2 layers is equally important, and fundamentally, to eliminate such phenomena, focus must be directed toward the L0 layer.

We have already devoted the majority of this article to discussing, from both theoretical and empirical perspectives, how viewing Hentai and extreme pornography impacts the individual at the micro level. Theoretically, individuals internalize sexual crimes depicted in media by spectacularizing sexual assault, engaging in female kawaii-ization, corrupting cognitive defenses through moral disengagement, and ultimately learning sexual scripts. Empirically, we have incorporated multiple academic journal studies utilizing cross-sectional or longitudinal research on various forms of pornography and objectifying media, which validate and extend our theoretical framework, demonstrating that the cognitive impacts of such viewing are traceable and that, compared to live-action pornography, animated pornography may present greater cognitive risks. Taken together, these findings suggest that viewing extreme pornography may continually produce 'potential perpetrators.'

It is important to understand that, based on sexual scripts, an individual can simulate behaviors experienced by others as their own perjury; when such behaviors are internalized cognitively, they may gradually be organized as executable processes during the rehearsal of fantasies. In the cross-sectional study on Hentai, it was found that the viewing frequency of Hentai can predict acceptance of rape myths and sexual assault strategies, which underscores its significance. This indicates that if individuals who view Hentai also exhibit high acceptance of rape myths and sexual assault strategies, regardless of the causal relationships among these factors, such individuals meet the criteria for classification as 'potential perpetrators' within this model.

This represents a dangerous trend. As exemplified by one case we have cited, Hentai, which frequently involves sexual crime and sexual domination, has ranked among the most popular content on the world's largest adult website, Pornhub, in recent years. This suggests that the number of viewers consuming such extreme pornography is extraordinarily large, and its dissemination has extended globally via the internet. Some contend that in Japan, the birthplace of animated pornography and regarded as one of the 'safest countries,' despite the development of its pornography industry, the sexual crime rate remains low.

³I argue that this is attributable to the concealment of sexual crimes against women within

³ Japan's laws on the 'crime of rape' underwent two progressive revisions in 2017 and 2023, with the latter legislation significantly altering the original statute. The scope was expanded from emphasizing non-consensual intercourse with women by violence or coercion to include acts that cause the victim (of any gender) to be in a condition where expressing, indicating, or realizing non-consent is difficult, or exploiting such a condition, to engage in sexual intercourse, oral sex, anal sex, or insertion of a body part (excluding the penis) or object into the vagina or anus with persons aged 16 or older (collectively referred to as the 'crime of sexual intercourse').

the country. From a single trend, one can discern the dark figures existing beneath the surface in Japan; following the 2023 legislative amendments in Japan, the number of recognized cases in Japanese police statistics categorized as “non-consensual sexual intercourse, etc.” increased from 1,655 cases in 2022 to 2,711 cases, reflecting an approximate 63.8% growth within one year; Including data from 2024, this increase compared to 2022 has reached approximately 2.4 times [116].

The rapid and substantial rise in sexual crime cases is not due to an actual increase in offenders or a worsening of crime severity in recent years, but because the scope of criminal offenses has been corrected to its proper extent, enabling victims who were previously marginalized and condemned to finally gain the legal confidence to come forward. Based on its growth trend, Japan's extensive sexual crime pyramid is expected to gradually become apparent. Hence, the purported low reporting rate of sexual crimes in Japan primarily refers to official statistics, which, given the low rate of sexual crime reporting in Japan, fails to fully reflect the actual circumstances.

2.7 Decomposition of L0 — Structurally high-risk individuals (Q1) and pornography-increment individuals (Q2)

To more clearly illustrate the impact of viewing such extreme pornography at the macro social level, further differentiation and screening of individuals at the L0 layer of the “Swiss Cheese × Pyramid” model is required. Firstly, it is essential to clarify that the L0 foundational layer of the model has long been grounded in a relatively stable base of individuals. These individuals predominantly stem from structural factors such as childhood abuse, domestic violence, hostile gender ideologies, and rape myths, and are unlikely to undergo significant changes in scale within a short timeframe, regardless of external influences. In other words, regardless of the presence of pornographic content (particularly extreme pornography), the social environment can firmly generate a group of 'potential perpetrators' through distorted sexual experiences and violence. We identify this as the relatively stable variable Q1.

In their systematic review article on risk factors for sexual violence entitled *A Systematic Qualitative Review of Risk and Protective Factors for Sexual Violence Perpetration*, Tharp et al. categorize the risk factors for sexual violence according to the social-ecological model into three domains: the personal layer, the relational layer (family, peers, intimate relationships), and the social layer. Drawing on 191 published empirical studies, they identified 42 factors at the personal layer, 23 at the relational layer, and 2 at the social layer. Among these 67 factors, 35 exhibit a consistently significant correlation with sexual violence perpetration across multiple rigorous investigations (Tharp et al., 2013). Based on a further examination of 35 relevant factors, Tharp et al. ultimately classified two groups of 'risk constellations' (constellations): one

identified as 'the existence and acceptance of violence,' and the other as 'unhealthy sexual behavior' (Tharp et al., 2013). The text contends that these two domains of factors are closely interconnected yet are frequently omitted from prevention programs. What exactly do these two domains encompass?

In summary, from the perspective of 'the existence and acceptance of violence,' at the personal layer, rationalization of violence and experiences of victimization through sexual violence may influence the perpetration of sexual violence at the personal level; at the relational and social levels, conflicts within the original family, supportive or encouraging attitudes of relatives and friends toward sexual violence, and experiences of childhood abuse may also constitute potential factors contributing to individual violent behavior. That is, if an individual grows up in an environment saturated with violence, where such violence is considered normal, they are more likely to develop attitudes supporting the use of violence, thereby increasing the likelihood of perpetrating sexual violence (Tharp et al., 2013).

By contrast, 'unhealthy sexual behavior' focuses on the individual and relational layers. Risks emerge if the individual regards sex as non-intimate and motivated solely by conquest or pleasure, holds antagonistic or hostile beliefs toward the opposite sex, engages in sexual activity due to peer pressure, or has a history of childhood sexual assault; these identity characteristics significantly increase the probability of perpetrating sexual violence (Tharp et al., 2013).

The crucial point is that these risk factors are by no means isolated cases. Researchers emphasize that many risk factors have been consistently validated across different age groups and samples. Clearly, among the numerous risk factors outlined by Tharp, even setting aside content such as 'exposure to pornographic media,' structural factors including childhood abuse, domestic violence, and hostile gender attitudes alone are sufficient to repeatedly generate a cohort of high-risk individuals across diverse cultural contexts (Tharp et al., 2013). This supports our Q1 hypothesis, which is not without foundation, demonstrating that under various media configurations, high-risk populations can be continually produced through the interplay of the gender system, domestic violence governance, poverty levels, and deficiencies in community environments. The governance of such risks constitutes a prolonged and arduous marathon, necessitating gradual improvements through gender equality education and social policy. In summary, Q1 represents a relatively stable presence in the short term with slow change over the long term; it originates from structural social factors and constitutes the most stable 'potential individual' at the L0 grassroots level within this model.

Our designation of Q1 serves not only to represent the stable L0 base existing in reality due to environmental factors but also to differentiate it from potential perpetrators arising from exposure to extreme pornography. We must recognize that, in addition to the relatively stable

variable Q1, there exists an incremental group whose size varies according to the scale of the pornographic industry and the extent of exposure to sexual domination and sexual crime; this group, which internalizes rape myths and sexual violence scripts through frequent exposure to extreme pornographic content, is identified as Q2.

If the Q1 individual, shaped by domestic violence, peer support attitudes toward sexual assault, and perpetration tendencies, is regarded as a foundation unlikely to change in the short term, then Q2 fluctuates with the degree of extreme depiction in content and audience scale, forming, upon the existing Q1 solid foundation, a thickened zone driven by extreme pornography toward rape myths, aggressive sexual fantasy, and domination sexual scripts. Although it cannot decisively increase or decrease the original Q1 individuals, its key significance lies in its capacity to determine the additional scale of offending beyond the Q1 layer.

We can conceive that, in the current context where the pornography image industry is well-developed, the L0 layer of the sexual crime pyramid we observe is in fact based on the Q1 layer as a baseline, with an outward incremental expansion corresponding to Q2. We all learned in elementary school that the area of a triangle equals the base multiplied by the height divided by two. Now, assuming the height remains constant, what would be the consequence if the base of this sexual crime risk pyramid increased alongside the expansion of Q2? This is illustrated in the figure below.

The answer is evident: the overall area of the pyramid, as well as the areas of each stratum, will correspondingly increase. The expansion of Q2 within L0 correspondingly broadens. The expansion of Q2 not only means that more 'potential perpetrators' enter this model but also

causes the degrees of harm at the L1, L2, and L3 layers to increase proportionally. The resulting effect is clear: the number of sexual crimes will subsequently rise, producing a new incremental segment. This is what I aim to demonstrate—the impact that extreme pornographic content and Hentai can have on the scale of sexual crime at the social level.

A manifest point is that if Q1 is a marathon requiring long-term governance through gender equality policies, then the growth of Q2 indicates that by promptly restricting, suspending streaming, delisting, or even enacting relevant laws against extreme pornographic content depicting rape, humiliation, and sexual assault, the growth of the Q2 segment can be curtailed relatively quickly. This would further reduce the base number of the Q2 layer, thereby fundamentally preventing certain sexual crimes and diminishing the perpetration at higher levels.

This model does not engage with the argument that 'not every individual who views pornography becomes a rapist'; rather, after affirming the objective fact that some individuals who consume extreme content do not necessarily engage in criminal behavior, it rigorously supports this claim through empirical data analysis grounded in sound logical reasoning, thereby presenting a coherent, self-contained model of sexual crime that does not require wholesale dismissal. It classifies sexual crimes according to a broad legal and social severity scale, proportionally grading them from the most prevalent fantasies and attitudes, demonstrating how individuals may gradually progress through vulnerabilities in defensive mechanisms—referred to as 'holes'—ultimately evolving into sexual crimes; Furthermore, through stratification and the combination of theory and research, high-risk individuals within social stability production are defined as Q1, which, as the foundational layer L0, serve as common sources for escalation into sexual crime; Secondly, individuals at high risk due to prolonged exposure to extreme pornography are defined as Q2, which constitute an additional intensified zone and fluctuate according to the scale of the pornography industry and the audience size for extreme content.

Epilogue: Human rights, fear, freedom

Japan, as one of the countries with the most developed global industries, has adult-oriented anime and games occupying a significant share of the overall media market, with the consumer base predominantly male. This segment of the ACG market remains unregulated by the government, relying solely on a fragile model of 'industry self-discipline.' Such a development approach facilitates the dissemination and promotion of extreme content involving humiliation, rape, and sexual assault, resulting in the covert yet perilous expansion of the Q2 tier of the sexual crime pyramid in certain domestic and international contexts.

In 2013, Japan's Liberal Democratic Party (LDP) submitted an amendment to the 'Child

Pornography Prohibition Act' to the Diet, wherein Article 2 of the supplementary provisions required the government to undertake investigative research into the relationship between creative works such as 'manga akin to child pornography' and violations of children's rights, with a review scheduled within three years to determine the necessity of regulatory inclusion; However, this provision was ultimately abandoned without prosecution due to strong opposition from the manga industry and academia[117]. Accordingly, following the partial amendments to the 'Law on Punishment of Acts Relating to Child Prostitution and Child Pornography and the Protection of Children' promulgated on June 25, 2014, the authorities explicitly declared that virtual pornographic content involving child images would not be subject to prosecution[118]. Although ordinary individuals may feel discomfort when viewing depictions of sexual assault against child characters in animation, this ineffable discomfort ultimately provided an opening for opponents, who eventually weaponized the so-called 'freedom of expression' guaranteed by Article 21 of the Japanese Constitution. What I did was, upon experiencing this physiological discomfort, to transform it into tangible evidence and forge it into a weapon. Freedom should not be founded upon the oppression of others; otherwise, it will inevitably become the freedom of the oppressor.

The 32nd President of the United States, Franklin Delano Roosevelt, in his State of the Union address on January 6, 1941—one year before Japan's attack on Pearl Harbor—famously known as the 'Four Freedoms' speech, listed 'Freedom from fear' alongside freedom of speech and expression, freedom of worship, and freedom from want, emphasizing that the populace has the right to freedom from aggression by foreign powers [119]. The concept of the “Four Freedoms” proposed by Roosevelt ultimately became a fundamental pillar of the 1948 Universal Declaration of Human Rights [120]. Regarding freedom from fear, Mary Kalemkerian of the Office of the United Nations High Commissioner for Human Rights stated: “This means that when you go to sleep at night, you can expect your house to still be there the next day.” [121]

Indeed, when we fixate on so-called “freedom of speech” and “creative freedom,” we must not forget the extensive community of victims who are also entitled to freedom from fear and anxiety caused by walking at night, malicious body gaze, physical harassment, or potential sexual assault by others. Just as cosplayers at comic conventions should not have to restrict their activities or seek protection from peers due to others' malicious behavior, an individual's bodily safety as a fundamental human right must not be subordinated to certain individuals' alleged “fantasy” or “creative” freedom. If such permissive freedom is predicated on potential harm to women, it must be restricted and regulated. In contemporary Japan, the right to “freedom,” originally intended to resist authoritarian censorship and to extend the boundaries of artistic expression, seems to have been co-opted by some as an all-encompassing justification for defending extreme sexual violence fantasies; we have thoroughly dismantled

this protective shield and exposed the true nature of such so-called “harmless fantasies” to public scrutiny.

From this perspective, the prolonged inaction of Japanese legislators and governmental institutions regarding extreme pornography in recent years is no longer a mere minor issue attributed to 'cultural characteristics' or 'industry preferences,' but constitutes a violation of individual human rights and a betrayal of the fundamental purpose of 'freedom.' When extreme pornography is normalized within culture and packaged as the 'innocent fantasy' of leisure entertainment, it often exacerbates the reality in which women are sexually assaulted and regarded as objects of sexual domination and sexual harassment. Japan, which continuously emphasizes 'respect for and protection of human rights' on the international stage, has long maintained a laissez-faire attitude toward extreme pornography and the sexualization of minors, leaving the depiction of extreme sexual violence to market forces. Such behavior itself constitutes an expansion and normalization of extreme pornography and, within this model, of Q2. Truly responsible liberal systems should understand that when 'creative freedom' conflicts with 'freedom from fear,' **the right to live free from violence and fear clearly must take precedence over the individual's right to express violent fantasies through creative work.**

Afterword

"May the long night give way to dawn; may the flowers bloom."

I no longer remember how long ago I began to experience such anger and pain. I have been a withdrawn child, at least since coming abroad. Shortly thereafter, I was diagnosed with depression and began taking antidepressants such as fluoxetine, and was at one point involuntarily hospitalized for treatment. By the glass window of the hospital bed, the setting sun signaled the end of the day and made my world completely devoid of light. I believed that nothing could ever pull me out of the darkness again.

Yet during those bleak and joyless days, it was that lily flower that gave me the strength to continue; Japan's ACG culture itself is sufficiently enchanting to captivate, and I happened to be one of those captivated. However, what I truly cherish is the unconventional 'yuri' within ACG culture; I admire the beautiful emotions portrayed in female-female relationships—that is the handholding during a romantic aquarium date, the inadvertent closeness on the sunset train, the bond forged amidst the ravages of war. They kiss while falling, perceive each other's heartbeat in the cold winter, and greet happiness at the fireworks festival. In that moment, I vowed that I alone must protect this flower.

Rather, it was yuri that granted me a second life.

Therefore, when witnessing attempts to defile and trample upon it—when the emotions between women are distorted into fetishes of domination and submission to the phallus as an

expression of sensuality—I, like all yuri enthusiasts, feel anger and distress, yet ultimately a sense of nihilism. The debate ultimately devolves into an outpouring of emotion; if this ongoing vitriol persists, I will eventually exhaust myself. However, whenever I see the tear stains left by girls who have been violated, their pained moans during rape, I realize that those feelings are real. If society's cognition of virtual women in the two-dimensional realm as manipulable and violable sex objects is not eradicated, and if sexual crimes continue to be packaged as entertainment features or gameplay without restriction or censorship, tragedy will repeatedly be enacted upon those I hold dear, despite their inherent potential to challenge the gender order.

At this juncture, I embarked on my journey, embarking upon the long and arduous path ahead. Throughout the autumn and winter terms on campus, while other students engaged in banter and conversation, I was engrossed in literature and note-taking; unyielding despite the biting cold wind. In the stillness of the late night, while neighbors slept soundly, I studied the works of Marx and Engels; steadfast despite the encroaching drowsiness. Along this protracted journey, I realized that what I sought to protect was not merely a single lily, but the multitude of women subjected to sexualization, objectification, and commodification. Thereafter, I transformed my pen into a spear, wielding theoretical thought as the sharpest weapon to compose this extensive essay. Due to my limited capability, despite reading numerous documents repeatedly, I have only a superficial understanding, and I rely on AI for research. I have often questioned myself: will anyone actually read what I write? Will it truly be meaningful? My response is that the very act of writing constitutes meaning. Even if it cannot bring about immediate change, it signifies that I no longer choose silence.

I believe that having embarked upon this path, I shall not turn back.

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This article uses only publicly available materials; sensitive visuals are mosaicked or cropped and not redistributed; no personally identifiable information is collected.

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